

A General Fine-Grained Reduction Theory for Effect Handlers

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Abstract

Effect handlers are a modern and increasingly popular approach to structuring computational effects in functional programming languages. However, while their traditional context-capturing operational semantics is well-suited to implementation tasks, it is less ideal as a reduction theory. We therefore introduce a fine-grained reduction theory for deep effect handlers, inspired by an existing reduction theory for `shift0`, along with a standard reduction strategy. We relate this strategy to the context-capturing operational semantics via a simulation argument, and show that the reduction theory preserves observational equivalence with respect to the classical semantics of handlers, thus allowing its use as a rewriting theory for handler-equipped programming languages—this rewriting system mostly coincides with previously studied type-based optimisations. In the process, we establish theoretical properties of our reduction theory, including confluence and standardisation theorems, adapting and extending existing techniques. Finally, we demonstrate the utility of our semantics by providing the first normalization-by-evaluation algorithm for effect handlers, expressed both as an abstract machine and as a higher-order normalizer, and we prove its soundness and completeness. Additionally, we establish non-expressibility of the lift operator, found in some effect-handler calculi, by the other constructs.

1 Introduction

Effect handlers provide a modern, modular approach to integrating effectful computation in functional programming languages. Based on the pioneering work of (Plotkin and Power 2004) on algebraic effects, and Plotkin and Pretnar’s idea of reifying algebras as *handlers* (Plotkin and Pretnar 2013), the technique has seen considerable rise in popularity, with several experimental languages developed (Bauer and Pretnar 2015; Biernacki et al. 2019; Brachthäuser et al. 2020; Convent et al. 2020; Leijen 2017a; Zhang and Myers 2019) and a successful integration within industrial functional languages (Sivaramakrishnan et al. 2021). However, despite its highly semantic and theoretical background, certain aspects of the approach, particularly as they relate to operational semantics, remain somewhat understudied. In this paper, we attempt to reduce this gap by developing a reduction theory for effect handlers, together with some applications.

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52 *Motivating example.* Consider the following program fragment, written in a pseudocode that
 53 could be interpreted in most programming languages that provide effect handlers:

```
54 handle  

55   iter (fn x -> let y = ask () in tell (x + y)) [1, 2, 3]  

56 with  

57   | ask () -> resume 5  

58   | return () -> ()
```

60 In the above, we assume a standard `iter` function that applies its first argument to the
 61 elements of the list in turn (for their side effects), and two *operations*: `ask` and `tell`. These
 62 have no interpretation on their own—their behaviour is determined by *handlers* that can
 63 be found, dynamically, in their evaluation context. The handler for the `ask` operation is
 64 provided: its intended semantics is to resume computation in the place where the operation
 65 was encountered with a constant value of 5. The other operation, on the other hand, is left
 66 uninterpreted by this fragment of the code—it may well be unknown at this point if, for
 67 instance, the snippet is the body of a function.

69 To a knowledgeable observer, the intent of this toy example is clear: since the provided
 70 handler for `ask` is benign and the environment can never insert a different handler between the
 71 operations and the provided one, the program fragment should be equivalent to the following,
 72 simpler one:

```
74   tell 6; tell 7; tell 8
```

76 Indeed, in an appropriate system (with a static type-and-effect system) we could use known
 77 reasoning techniques, such as the logical relation of Biernacki et al. (2018), to establish
 78 that the two are observationally equivalent.¹ However, this would be an (admittedly trivial)
 79 instance of a sophisticated reasoning technique that is not necessarily easy to automate.
 80 Maybe a compiler could transform the first snippet into the second one as an optimisation
 81 based simply on specialisation of program fragments?

83 To consider this question, we must first recall the semantics of effect handlers. There are
 84 two known approaches to reducing operations with matching handlers: the first, developed
 85 by Kammar et al. (2013), attaches a continuation to an operation when it is found during
 86 evaluation, and extends it with pieces of the evaluation context until the matching handler is
 87 reached, with the gathered continuation taking the role of the *resumption*, which is passed to
 88 the body of the enclosing handler. While this approach reflects the denotational presentation
 89 of algebraic effects, it is not optimal as a foundation for a reduction theory. We discuss its
 90 relationship with our approach in the following; however, we now focus on the other known
 91 approach to computing with handlers, which is an adaptation of context-sensitive reduction
 92 semantics for delimited control, due to Leijen (2017a).

94 In this approach, the gist of the crucial reduction rule is that when we encounter an
 95 operation, the rule looks through the evaluation context until a matching handler is found,
 96 and only then reifies the intervening part as a resumption. This resumption, together with
 97 the argument of the operation are then passed to the body of the handler, as in the previous
 98 approach. In the case of our program fragment, the evaluation would look as follows: first,
 99 the standard definition of `iter` is unfolded, giving rise to the following snippet:

100
 101 ¹In fact, it would be easy to prove a more general result that would hold for any input list.
 102

```

103   handle
104     let y = ask () in tell (1 + y);
105     iter (fn x -> let y = ask () in tell (x + y)) [2, 3]
106   with
107     | ask () -> resume 5
108     | return () -> ()
109

```

Now, the operation is in the evaluation position, and its matching handler can be found. Since the argument of the operation is trivial, the only interesting aspect is the resumption that gets captured and passed to the handler, giving us the following result:

```

114   (fn z ->
115     handle
116       let y = z in tell (1 + y);
117       iter (fn x -> let y = ask () in tell (x + y)) [2, 3]
118     with
119       | ask () -> resume 5
120       | return () -> ()) 5
121

```

Note that the `handle` expression is retained within the resumption: this is a characteristic feature of *deep* effect handlers, with which we will concern ourselves in this development.

We can now reduce the application of the resumption to its argument, and proceed with evaluation to get the following snippet:

```

128   handle
129     tell 6; iter (fn x -> let y = ask () in tell (x + y)) [2, 3]
130   with
131     | ask () -> resume 5
132     | return () -> ()
133

```

At this point, however, the operation `tell` is in the evaluation position, and we have no matching handler. No other reduction (save for unfolding `iter` on the tail of the list) can apply, and thus we cannot reach the simpler result.

This example, while clearly artificial, exposes inherent limitations that the standard operational semantics of deep effect handlers imposes on program optimisation through specialisation. The presence of an uninterpreted operation (or, indeed, an uninterpreted variable in the function position of an open program fragment) “freezes” any handlers in its evaluation context, and prevents us from reducing them, thus limiting the possibilities of compiling out known effects into more efficient, pure code. Can we avoid these problems and obtain the simpler program, without any trace of the `ask` operation or its associated handler?

Fine-grained reduction. It turns out that if we choose an appropriate reduction theory, such optimisation becomes possible. In fact, one set of rewrite rules that can be used to optimise programs has been proposed by Saleh (2019) and taken up by Karachalias et al. (2021). While their focus is on optimising the general form of calls to recursive, effectful functions wrapped in an effect handler—in the context of our motivating example, calls of the shape `handle iter ... xs with ...`, where `xs` may be a general expression—this task

153

requires them to consider more local rules for program simplification as well.² Independently, Biernacki et al. (2021) proposed a similar set of rules as a *bona fide* reduction theory in the context of delimited-control operators. The core idea behind both sets of rules is to define the reduction of the delimiter (respectively, `$` or `handle` construct for the two types of delimited control) through its interactions with other computation formers, notably the `let` expressions. In this approach, rather than form the resumption only when an operation is encountered, a handler would “distribute” through the `let` expression, appropriately adjusting its `return` clause (which determines the result if the computation within the handler terminates with a value). In our example, the reduction (after unfolding the `iter` function) could proceed as follows:

```

165   handle
166     let y = ask () in tell (1 + y)
167   with
168     | ask () -> resume 5
169     | return () ->
170       handle
171         iter (fn x -> let y = ask () in tell (x + y)) [2, 3]
172       with
173         | ask () -> resume 5
174         | return () -> ()

```

Note how the handler gets duplicated as the iteration over the tail of the list gets incorporated into the `return` clause. This may seem worrisome from the point of view of evaluation (and we address these concerns in Section 2); however, it also unlocks the possibility of further reduction, which was prohibited by the traditional approach. Following on, we get:

```

181   handle ask ()
182   with
183     | ask () -> resume 5
184     | return y ->
185       handle tell (1 + y)
186     with
187       | ask () -> resume 5
188       | return () ->
189         handle iter (fn x -> let y = ask () in tell (x + y)) [2, 3]
190       with
191         | ask () -> resume 5
192         | return () -> ()

```

Now, since the handler matches the operation, we can continue—but there is no need to construct the resumption, since there can never be any intervening context. Thus, instead of a “resumption” we simply pass the argument and `return` clause to the body of the handler, obtaining:

```

199   handle tell (1 + 5)
200   with

```

²The general case they tackle is a proper compiler optimisation that cannot be naturally viewed as part of the reduction theory, and we do not aim to address it in the present paper.

```

205 | ask () -> resume 5
206 | return () ->
207   handle iter (fn x -> let y = ask () in tell (x + y)) [2, 3]
208   with
209     | ask () -> resume 5
210     | return () -> ()
211

```

212 This time, the operation within the handler does *not* match the handled operation. Again,
 213 there is no need to capture the handler, even though the evaluation of `tell 6` cannot proceed.
 214 Instead, we simply sequence the computation of the `return` clause after the control-stuck
 215 operation, obtaining:

```

216 tell 6;
217 handle iter (fn x -> let y = ask () in tell (x + y)) [2, 3]
218 with
219   | ask () -> resume 5
220   | return () -> ()
221

```

222 Now we can continue the reduction process for the tail of the list, which leads to removing
 223 all instances of `ask` (and its associated handler) altogether. In this paper, we introduce and
 224 study a calculus that makes optimisations like the one described above possible.
 225

226 *Structure of the paper and contributions.* The remainder of the paper is structured as follows.
 227 In Section 2 we develop a core calculus of deep effect handlers, in the style of Piróg et al.
 228 (2019). We equip it with two sets of semantics: a context-capturing one, based on capturing
 229 parts of the evaluation context as resumptions as outlined above, and a fine-grained one,
 230 which draws on the optimisation rules of Saleh (2019) and the reduction theory of Biernacki
 231 et al. (2021). We also establish a non-expressibility result for the *lift* construct, which was a
 232 feature of some of the systems to date, but whose precise expressive power was not formally
 233 studied before. In Section 3 we establish bisimilarity between the traditional semantics and
 234 the fine-grained rules, treated as evaluation theories. Thus, we provide a connection between
 235 the two sets of semantics of the deep handlers. In Sections 4 and 5 we treat the fine-grained
 236 contraction rules as a basis of a *reduction* theory by allowing the reduction rules to be
 237 performed in general contexts, and establish key properties of the calculus that ensure it is a
 238 sensible reduction theory: the confluence and standardisation results. In this, we follow classic
 239 approaches from lambda calculus, and extend them to our setup to account for new challenges
 240 posed by the effect handlers. These results allow us to establish, in Section 6, fine-grained
 241 equational reasoning as a sound tool to reason about observational equivalence with respect
 242 to the traditional semantics, formally justifying Saleh’s basic optimisations without recourse
 243 to types. Finally, in Section 7 we develop the first normalization-by-evaluation procedure for
 244 effect handlers, based on the fine-grained reduction, that takes the form of an abstract machine,
 245 and we prove its soundness and completeness with respect to the fine-grained reduction
 246 theory. In Section 8 we discuss the most relevant related work, and we conclude in Section 9.
 247 Additionally, the article contains Appendix A in which we show an OCaml implementation
 248 of the first-order normalizer of Section 7 as well as a higher-order normalizer that has been
 249 derived from the first-order one through the functional correspondence between higher-order
 250 evaluators and abstract machines (Ager et al. 2003). The implementations take advantage of
 251 OCaml’s GADTs and of a well-scoped representation of the syntax of the calculus.
 252
 253
 254
 255

256 $e, a ::= \text{return } v \mid \text{let } x = a \text{ in } e \mid u \ v \mid \text{do } v \mid \text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r \mid \text{lift } e$ (expressions)
 257
 258 $u, v, w, h, r ::= x \mid \lambda x. e$ (values)
 259

260 Fig. 1. The syntax of the handler calculi, shared between the context-capturing and the fine-grained
 261 semantics.

262
 263 *Formalization and implementation.* With the exception of the expressibility of lift in Section 2.4
 264 and the syntactic abstract machine in Section 2.3 all of the theoretical results presented in this
 265 paper are formalized in the Rocq interactive theorem prover. Both the formalization and the
 266 OCaml implementation of the normalizers are available at: [https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19254282)
 267 [19254282](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19254282).
 268

269
 270 *Relation to the conference version of this article.* This is a revised and extended version of
 271 the work published at ICFP 2023 (Sieczkowski et al. 2023). The proofs in Section 3 were
 272 reworked to fit better with the methodology used, which allowed us to significantly streamline
 273 and simplify presentation. We have modified the formulation of the syntactic abstract machine
 274 (in Section 2.3) and the normalizer (in Section 7) to better highlight the connections between
 275 the two and the reduction semantics and enhance the clarity of the presentation. We have
 276 also expanded the discussion of methodology and related work in all the technical sections.
 277 Finally, in Appendix A we have included a presentation of OCaml implementations of two
 278 normalizers based on the theory developed in this article.
 279

280 2 Syntax and semantics

281
 282 In this section, we introduce two calculi of algebraic effects that share the same syntax but
 283 are equipped with different operational semantics. The syntax, presented in Figure 1, is a
 284 fine-grain call-by-value λ -calculus (Levy et al. 2003), extended with algebraic-effect specific
 285 constructs—a common setup, used for instance by Hillerström et al. (2020) or Piróg et al.
 286 (2019).

287 More precisely, the syntax is stratified into two categories: values and expressions. Values
 288 comprise variables and λ -abstractions. Note that we do not need to handle recursive functions
 289 explicitly, as the calculi are untyped, and thus fixed-point combinators are easily expressible.
 290 Expressions represent possibly effectful computations. An expression may return a value,
 291 chain computations sequentially with a let-expression, apply a function to an argument
 292 (both need to be values), invoke an effect, handle an effectful computation (with h and r
 293 representing an effect handler and a return clause, respectively), or *lift* a computation. In
 294 contrast to the syntax used in the example in Section 1, the algebraic operations or effects are
 295 unnamed; we use the lift operator to allow a single expression to use multiple distinct effects.
 296 This is achieved through the lifted computation “skipping” the nearest enclosing handler,
 297 which allows us to encode examples such as the one presented in the introduction.
 298
 299

300 2.1 Context-capturing calculus

301
 302 The first calculus we consider is called λ_{cc} : it is an untyped version of a calculus of deep
 303 handlers considered by Piróg et al. (2019). The operational semantics of λ_{cc} is presented in
 304 Figure 2—it is given as a standard reduction semantics, where a redex can be contracted in
 305 any evaluation context. The contraction comprises the standard rules ($\beta.v$) and (let.v), as
 306

307	$K ::= [] \mid K[\text{let } x = [] \text{ in } e] \mid K[\text{lift } []] \mid K[\text{handle } [] \text{ with } h, r]$	(evaluation contexts)
308	$J_n ::= {}_{(n=0)} [] \mid \text{let } x = J_n \text{ in } e \mid {}_{(n=m+1)} \text{lift } J_m \mid \text{handle } J_{n+1} \text{ with } h, r$	(n -free contexts)
309	$R ::= \text{handle } J_0 \text{ with } h, r$	(resumptions)
310		
311		
312	$(\beta.v)$	$(\lambda x.e) v \mapsto_{\text{cc}} e[v/x]$
313	$(\text{let}.v)$	$\text{let } x = \text{return } v \text{ in } e \mapsto_{\text{cc}} e[v/x]$
314	$(\text{lift}.v)$	$\text{lift return } v \mapsto_{\text{cc}} \text{return } v$
315	$(\text{handle}.v)$	$\text{handle return } v \text{ with } h, r \mapsto_{\text{cc}} r v$
316	$(\text{handle}.c)$	$\text{handle } J_0[\text{do } v] \text{ with } h, r \mapsto_{\text{cc}} \text{let } f = h v \text{ in } f(\lambda x.\text{handle } J_0[\text{return } x] \text{ with } h, r)$
317		
318		
319	$\frac{e_1 \mapsto_{\text{cc}} e_2}{K[e_1] \mapsto_{\text{cc}} K[e_2]}$	
320		
321		
322		

Fig. 2. The traditional, context-capturing operational semantics of λ_{cc} .

well as rules that define the interaction of the handler and lift constructs with values and operations. This is simple in the case of values: handling a value (`handle.v`) consists in passing it to the return value (as no effects need to be handled), whereas lifting a value (`lift.v`) simply returns it (as no effects need to be lifted).

The most instrumental contraction rule of the calculus is (`handle.c`), which expresses the handling of an operation by a matching handler. In order to formalize the notion of a matching context, we introduce “free” evaluation contexts, J , which are indexed by their freeness level, i.e., the number of handlers surrounding the context hole that the context would need to neutralize any lift operators that surround the context hole to skip handlers. The definition of this indexed family is presented in the style of an attribute grammar: the nonterminal is indexed with a parameter, n , which in this case describes how “free” the context is. This parameter can change in the productions (e.g., in the production for `handle`), but it can also be *constrained* by an equation, which enforces that a given production can only produce contexts at some index (e.g., the $[]$ production builds a 0-free context). In essence, this is a compact notation for indexed families of types of the kind one might define in Rocq or Agda; we will use this notation throughout the paper. Whenever the index of an element of such an indexed family is constrained in any way or useful as a clarification, we include it; however, by convention, we drop it when it may be arbitrary.

For our contexts, we can see that in the grammar of J_n , `lift` increases the index (proceeding inside-out), whereas `handle` decreases it. Thus, balanced contexts are exactly 0-free contexts J_0 , and the handler surrounding such a context is the one that matches an operation performed within the context. The rule (`handle.c`) then contracts such a redex by passing the value given to the operation, v , to the handler h , and passing the captured and reified *resumption* (delimited continuation) to the result of the application—this needs to be expanded using a `let`-binder due to the fine-grained syntax. The resumption R comprises the 0-free context together with the surrounding `handle` expression; this context is reified as a value by plugging it with a variable bound by a lambda-abstraction on the outside. Capturing the context together with the enclosing handler is characteristic of deep handlers (as opposed to shallow handlers that capture a handler-free resumption (Hillerström et al. 2020)).

$$\begin{array}{l}
358 \quad E_k ::= {}_{(k=\top)} [] \mid {}_{(k=\top)} E_{\top}[\text{let } x = [] \text{ in } e] \mid {}_{(k=\top)} E_{\top}[\text{lift } []] \mid \\
359 \quad {}_{(k=\text{H})} E_{k'}[\text{handle } [] \text{ with } h, r] \quad \text{(evaluation contexts)} \\
360 \\
361 \quad \text{IVal } \ni i ::= \text{return } v \mid \text{let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \mid \text{do } v \mid \text{lift } e \quad \text{(intermediate values)} \\
362 \quad T_n ::= {}_{(n=0)} [] \mid \text{let } x = T_n \text{ in } e \mid {}_{(n=m+1)} \text{lift } T_m \quad \text{(resumption contexts)} \\
363 \\
364 \\
365 \\
366 \quad (\beta.v) \quad (\lambda x.e) v \mapsto_{\text{fg}}^k e[v/x] \\
367 \quad (\text{let}.v) \quad \text{let } x = \text{return } v \text{ in } e \mapsto_{\text{fg}}^{\top} e[v/x] \\
368 \quad (\text{lift}.v) \quad \text{lift return } v \mapsto_{\text{fg}}^{\top} \text{return } v \\
369 \quad (\text{handle}.v) \quad \text{handle return } v \text{ with } h, r \mapsto_{\text{fg}}^k r v \\
370 \quad (\text{handle}.do) \quad \text{handle do } v \text{ with } h, r \mapsto_{\text{fg}}^k \text{let } f = h v \text{ in } f r \\
371 \quad (\text{handle}.lift) \quad \text{handle lift } e \text{ with } h, r \mapsto_{\text{fg}}^k \text{let } x = e \text{ in } r x \\
372 \quad (\text{handle}.let) \quad \text{handle let } x = a \text{ in } e \text{ with } h, r \mapsto_{\text{fg}}^k \text{handle } a \text{ with } h, (\lambda x. \text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r) \\
373 \\
374 \\
375 \quad \frac{e_1 \mapsto_{\text{fg}}^k e_2}{E_k[e_1] \mapsto_{\text{fg}} E_k[e_2]} \quad \frac{e_1 \mapsto_{\text{fg}} e_2}{C[e_1] \mapsto_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}} C[e_2]} \\
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\end{array}$$

Fig. 3. The fine-grained operational semantics and reduction theory of λ_{fg} . Note that the kind of evaluation context E_k has to match the contraction, while the general reduction may use any contraction in any (possibly binding) context C .

The evaluation relation (\mapsto_{cc}) is then defined as a contextual closure of contraction with respect to the entire set of evaluation contexts K that subsume the n -free contexts J_n (as usual, $K[e]$ stands for K plugged with e).

2.2 Fine-grained calculus

The second calculus, λ_{fg} , builds on the twin lineage of Saleh’s optimization rules and Biernacki et al.’s reduction theory for delimited control to avoid explicit capture of contexts and facilitate optimization; it is presented in Figure 3. As with the context-capturing semantics, it is defined as a reduction semantics; however, this time the semantics encodes a *hybrid* evaluation strategy (Biernacka et al. 2017; García-Pérez and Nogueira 2014), i.e., its redexes and contraction rules available depend on the *kind* of the evaluation context within which they happen. We distinguish two of these kinds, \top and H , with the former standing for “top-level” contexts that do not contain handlers, while the latter, for “handling” contexts that contain at least one handler. The definition of the evaluation context matches this intuition: we can only extend a top-level evaluation context with a let-binding or a lift (and the resulting context is of kind \top), while any context can be extended with a handler (giving the result kind H).

Like the evaluation contexts themselves, contractions are also annotated with a kind: these determine in what evaluation context a given contraction may take place. The contraction of applications ($\beta.v$), let-expressions ($\text{let}.v$) and the lifting of values ($\text{lift}.v$) remain as in the context-capturing semantics, although, importantly, the latter two may only be used in a top-level context, as evidenced by the \top ascription on the rules. The remaining rules, both ($\beta.v$) and the rules that describe the action of handlers, may be used in any context.

409 The remaining four contractions describe the action of handlers on four kinds of *intermediate*
 410 *values*. These are expressions that are neither redexes, nor can be decomposed further within
 411 a handler (H-kinded) context—and thus, from the perspective of reduction of an H-kinded
 412 context *behave* like values. They comprise proper values, operations, and let- and lift-
 413 expressions. The action of handlers on values (`handle.v`) remains as before: we simply pass
 414 the value to the return clause. The interaction with operations (`handle.do`) can be much
 415 simpler than in the context-capturing case, since we only need to consider an operation
 416 *directly* within a handler, with no evaluation context separating the two. This allows us
 417 to rewrite `handle do v` with h, r as $h v r$ —which, due to the highly stylized presentation of
 418 our calculus, we take as syntactic sugar for a let-expression `let f = h v in f r`. Note that r
 419 is passed to h as the second argument, which means that at this stage it represents the
 420 resumption: in particular, there is no need to duplicate the handler at this point or reify a
 421 context by creating a fresh lambda-abstraction. The action of handlers on the lift-expressions
 422 (`handle.lift`) is also straightforward due to the lack of intervening context: the expression
 423 within the lift has no access to the handler (as any operations within ought to skip over that
 424 handler). Thus, the handler can be dropped, contracting `handle lift e` with h, r to $r e$, which
 425 we write `let x = e in r x` in the fine-grained calculus. Finally, we consider the interaction of
 426 handlers with let-expressions (`handle.let`), which is the most complex contraction rule of
 427 the fine-grained semantics, and the one that enforces its *deep* treatment of handlers. It states
 428 that a handler can be *distributed* to the subcomputations of a let-expression `let x = a in e`,
 429 by appropriately updating the return clause r of the handler with e enclosed with a copy of
 430 the handler the reduction started with. This enforces the intuition about deep handlers that
 431 both operations in a and in e should be handled in the same way by explicitly duplicating
 432 the handler. Effectively, each use of the (`handle.let`) rule closes the distance between an
 433 effect call or a lift operation and its handler—until they face each other directly and can be
 434 eliminated with either the (`handle.do`) or the (`handle.lift`) rule.
 435
 436
 437

438 Besides the operational semantics, which can be used to evaluate terms, we introduce a
 439 general reduction relation, written $\longrightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{g}}}$. This relation arises as the closure of both kinds of
 440 contractions under arbitrary, possibly binding, contexts C . Thus, it allows us to perform all
 441 the evaluation contractions, both in evaluation positions and under binders—but it also allows
 442 us to use T-kinded contractions (such as (`let.v`)) under handlers, i.e., in contexts that would
 443 otherwise be H-kinded. This reduction relation corresponds to Saleh’s optimization rules; we
 444 study this relation and its connection to the fine-grained evaluation in Sections 4 and 5.
 445

446 In addition to evaluation contexts, which are indexed by kinds, as mentioned before, we
 447 also define *resumption contexts*, T_n , indexed with natural numbers that determine how many
 448 times the lift operation occurs within them. These are isomorphic to the top-level evaluation
 449 contexts, E_{\top} , but they also mirror the n -free contexts of the capturing semantics, J_n in some
 450 ways. They are, however, much more restricted due to the nature of the fine-grained reduction.
 451 These will be used in Section 3 to relate the two semantics to each other, but play no direct
 452 role in the operational semantics.
 453

454 *Discussion.* With the semantics defined above, we discuss some of the features of our fine-
 455 grained semantics, as well as their relation to prior work and possibilities that this framework
 456 may unlock. Firstly, both (`handle.do`) and (`handle.let`) correspond directly to rewrite rules
 457 given by (Saleh 2019) (respectively, rules WITH-HANDLED-OP and WITH-DO in Figure 3.2);
 458 (`handle.lift`) plays the same role as his WITH-PURE, but in a purely syntax-directed, untyped
 459

Fig. 4. Comparison of evaluation in the context-capturing and fine-grained semantics. Fine-grained semantics needs three evaluation steps to arrive at a handler call (lower path, annotated with *fg*), while a single nonlocal evaluation step is sufficient (upper path, annotated with *cc*). There is a mismatch between the captured resumptions that can be mitigated by two general reduction steps (dashed arrows, fine-grained reductions).

setting, which makes it more applicable as a basis for a reduction theory. Thus, one could consider our semantics an elevation of a variant of these rules from the position of admissible equations/optimisations in a language to the position of rules that define the semantics.

One consequence of such a treatment that is worth noting is that our architecture of the reduction system immediately precludes any direct extension to shallow handlers (Hillerström and Lindley 2018), whose semantics assumes that the handler is never copied to the resumption. In our setting, the rule (*handle.let*) eagerly does exactly that, while a shallow handler can only be used in *one* of the two branches of a *let*-expression.

The reduction rules we propose resemble other reduction theories for calculi of delimited control that are based on piece-by-piece consumption of evaluation contexts (Felleisen 1988; Pretnar 2015). However, in those works the control operator or the operation aggregates the elementary contexts on the way to its surrounding delimiter or handler. In contrast, our calculus consumes the context in the opposite direction, i.e, from the handler to the operation, and we take advantage of the return clause of the handler to store the elementary contexts guarded by (possibly superfluous) handlers. While such semantics will likely be able to reduce programs such as the example in the introduction, it is not clear that they would make for a clean reduction theory as the operations would tend to accumulate all the enclosing contexts as their continuations, giving the resulting programs something of a continuation-passing look.

As mentioned before, our fine-grained semantics is an example of a hybrid evaluation strategy. These strategies are typically used in the semantic specification of full normalization in λ -calculi (Biernacka et al. 2017; García-Pérez and Nogueira 2014). In contrast, here we use a hybrid nature of the semantics to distinguish between contractions allowed within handlers and the (larger) set of contractions allowed without.

The fact that the fine-grained semantics duplicates handlers very aggressively may not be the first choice for an implementation of an evaluator for a calculus of algebraic effects. It is, however, an interesting alternative to the context-capturing semantics that is more powerful when it comes to program rewriting and optimization, as illustrated with the motivating example in Section 1, and as a foundation for a fully-normalizing procedure (developed in

511 Section 7). The discrepancy between the two semantics in the case where open expressions
 512 are reduced is illustrated in Figure 4: note how both the context-capturing and fine-grained
 513 semantics reach an open-stuck term, but the captured resumption is much simpler in the
 514 fine-grained case. This simplification may be recovered using the reduction relation ($\longrightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}$,
 515 presented as dashed arrows in the figure). The intuition that the resumption captured by the
 516 context-capturing semantics may be reduced (in a particular way) to reach the resumption of
 517 the fine-grained semantics will be an important insight in the proof that the two semantics
 518 converge when evaluating closed terms, developed in Section 3.
 519

520 Finally, note that the fine-grained semantics allows us to consider whether the rule (lift.v),
 521 which is virtually unavoidable in the context-capturing semantics, is necessary or even
 522 desirable in fine-grained evaluation. It is never used in “well-handled” programs, where
 523 every lift operation will be tackled by a handler: in particular, this would always be the case in
 524 a type-and-effect safe setting. This means that in a non-type-safe setting one could decide that
 525 *any* lifted expression in a top-level evaluation context is control-stuck (and thus, that top-level
 526 contexts are only formed using let-expressions). We do not pursue the study of this variant
 527 semantics further in this paper for a simple reason: we want to establish bisimilarity of our
 528 two semantics, which would not hold if we abandoned the rule (lift.v). However, exploring
 529 this choice could be an interesting direction for future work.
 530

531 In the following subsection we present an additional view on the evaluation relation in the
 532 fine-grained calculus, offered by a syntactic abstract machine. The abstract machine and the
 533 simulation theorems developed in the following section shed light on the inner workings of
 534 the new semantics and explain the architecture of the new calculus in greater detail.
 535

536 2.3 A syntactic abstract machine

537 In this section we present a *syntactic* abstract machine for the fine-grained calculus that is
 538 constructed in the spirit of the CK machine (Felleisen et al. 2009). The main goal here is to
 539 show how in the new semantics the expressions are decomposed depending on the presence of
 540 a handler. A more realistic abstract machine, equipped with environments and other semantic
 541 components can be found in Section 7.
 542

543 The syntactic abstract machine in Figure 5 corresponds through Danvy and Nielsen’s
 544 refocusing method (Biernacka et al. 2017; Danvy and Nielsen 2004) to a naive implementation
 545 of the fine-grained reduction semantics presented above. In such a naive implementation
 546 computations are organized into a decompose-contract-recompose loop. However, when a
 547 calculus under consideration enjoys the unique-decomposition property, i.e., each non-value
 548 expression can be uniquely decomposed into a (potential) redex and an evaluation context,
 549 the loop can be optimised to avoid the unnecessary term recomposition after a redex has
 550 been contracted, leading to a transition system, typically called an abstract machine, in which
 551 term decomposition restarts from the contraction site. In our case, as already mentioned, the
 552 reduction semantics enjoys the unique-decomposition property and therefore it lends itself to
 553 refocusing, taking into account the fact that it is also hybrid (Biernacka et al. 2017)—the
 554 intermediate values i , as defined in Figure 3, are interpreted differently depending on whether
 555 there is a handler they can interact with or not.
 556

557 The syntactic abstract machine operates in six different modes:

- 558 • in $\langle e \mid E \rangle_e$, based on the structure of e , the machine either installs a handler on E ,
- 559 or it identifies a potential $(\beta.v)$ -redex that will be taken care of through a dedicated

$$\begin{aligned}
562 \quad & \langle \text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r \mid E \rangle_e \triangleright \langle e \mid E[\text{handle } \square \text{ with } h, r] \rangle_e \\
563 \quad & \langle v_1 v_2 \mid E \rangle_e \triangleright \langle v_1 \mid v_2 \mid E \rangle_a \\
564 \quad & \langle i \mid E \rangle_e \triangleright \langle E \mid i \rangle_k \\
565 \quad & \langle \lambda x. e \mid v \mid E \rangle_a \triangleright \langle e[v/x] \mid E \rangle_e \\
566 \quad & \langle E[\text{handle } \square \text{ with } h, r] \mid i \rangle_k \triangleright \langle i \mid h \mid r \mid E \rangle_h \\
567 \quad & \langle E_{\top} \mid i \rangle_k \triangleright \langle i \mid E_{\top} \rangle_t \\
568 \quad & \langle \text{return } v \mid h \mid r \mid E \rangle_h \triangleright \langle r \mid v \mid E \rangle_a \\
569 \quad & \langle \text{let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \mid h \mid r \mid E \rangle_h \triangleright \langle e_1 \mid E[\text{handle } \square \text{ with } h, \lambda x. \text{handle } e_2 \text{ with } h, r] \rangle_e \\
570 \quad & \langle \text{do } v \mid h \mid r \mid E \rangle_h \triangleright \langle E \mid \text{let } x = h v \text{ in } x r \rangle_k \\
571 \quad & \langle \text{lift } e \mid h \mid r \mid E \rangle_h \triangleright \langle E \mid \text{let } x = e \text{ in } r.x \rangle_k \\
572 \quad & \langle \text{return } v \mid E_{\top} \rangle_t \triangleright \langle E_{\top} \mid v \rangle_{vt} \\
573 \quad & \langle \text{let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \mid E_{\top} \rangle_t \triangleright \langle e_1 \mid E_{\top}[\text{let } x = \square \text{ in } e_2] \rangle_e \\
574 \quad & \langle \text{lift } e \mid E_{\top} \rangle_t \triangleright \langle e \mid E_{\top}[\text{lift } \square] \rangle_e \\
575 \quad & \langle E_{\top}[\text{let } x = \square \text{ in } e] \mid v \rangle_{vt} \triangleright \langle e[v/x] \mid E_{\top} \rangle_e \\
576 \quad & \langle E_{\top}[\text{lift } \square] \mid v \rangle_{vt} \triangleright \langle E_{\top} \mid v \rangle_{vt}
\end{aligned}$$

Fig. 5. An abstract machine for fine-grained operational semantics. The machine starts in the configuration $\langle e \mid \square \rangle_e$. The final configurations are: $\langle \square \mid v \rangle_{vt}$, representing a computed value v , $\langle \text{do } v \mid E_{\top} \rangle_t$, representing a control-stuck term $E_{\top}[\text{do } v]$, and $\langle x \mid v \mid E \rangle_a$, representing an open stuck term $E[x v]$.

mode, or it encounters an intermediate value i and delegates its processing to another mode;

- in $\langle v_1 \mid v_2 \mid E \rangle_a$ the machine contracts a redex according to the rule $(\beta.v)$ or it gets stuck if v_1 is a variable;
- in $\langle E \mid i \rangle_k$ the machine inspects the context E , finding a redex if it contains a handler (i.e., when it is of kind H) or continuing to process i in a context is of kind T;
- in $\langle i \mid h \mid r \mid E \rangle_h$ the machine contracts the redex according to one of the four contraction rules: $(\text{handle}.v)$, $(\text{handle}.let)$, $(\text{handle}.do)$, $(\text{handle}.lift)$;
- in $\langle i \mid E_{\top} \rangle_t$ the machine inspects i and either decomposes it further (let and lift expressions), continues to process E_{\top} if a value is reached, or gets stuck when it encounters an unhandled operation (i.e., a do -expression);
- in $\langle E_{\top} \mid v \rangle_{vt}$ the machine contracts a top-level redex according to one of the two remaining contraction rules $(\text{let}.v)$ and $(\text{lift}.v)$, or it halts with a computed value v , if E_{\top} is empty.

The structure of the machine presented here is slightly different from the one presented in (Sieczkowski et al. 2023), where the evaluation context was divided into two: an inner one representing a possibly empty stack of handlers and an outer one representing the top-level context E_{\top} , i.e., the rest of the context beyond the outermost handler. An abstract machine with such a context structure was first defined for a calculus of delimited control (Materzok and Biernacki 2011). This modification is purely cosmetic, but we find the machine presented

in this work more concise and more evidently corresponding to the fine-grained reduction semantics. In both cases the machine uses a stack of handlers rather than a stack of expressions or partial continuations coupled with their handlers, which is one of the most notable differences with the more traditional abstract-machine semantics for handlers, e.g., in (Biernacki et al. 2019; Hillerström et al. 2020).

It is worth noting that the hybrid nature of the fine-grained semantics manifests itself in the abstract machine expressivity: the intermediate values are interpreted differently in the configurations $\langle i \mid h \mid r \mid E \rangle_h$ and $\langle i \mid E_T \rangle_t$.

Regarding the correctness of the abstract machine, it follows from the correctness of refocusing for hybrid reduction strategies (Biernacka et al. 2017):

THEOREM 2.1. *For any expression e ,*

- (1) $e \rightarrow_{\text{fg}}^* v$ if and only if $\langle e \mid \square \rangle_e \triangleright^* \langle \square \mid v \rangle_{\text{vt}}$
- (2) $e \rightarrow_{\text{fg}}^* E_T[\text{do } v]$ if and only if $\langle e \mid \square \rangle_e \triangleright^* \langle \text{do } v \mid E_T \rangle_t$
- (3) $e \rightarrow_{\text{fg}}^* E[x \ v]$ if and only if $\langle e \mid \square \rangle_e \triangleright^* \langle x \mid v \mid E \rangle_a$.

2.4 The expressive power of lift

The lift operator (Leijen 2017a) is a construct present in several calculi of effect handlers in the literature (Biernacki et al. 2018, 2019; Piróg et al. 2019), but its expressive power does not appear to have been formally investigated. In this section we show that lift is *not* eliminable, in the sense of Felleisen (1991), in the untyped calculi of deep handlers considered in this work. We work with λ_{cc} , but as we prove in Section 3, the two operational semantics are equivalent and the same reasoning can be carried out in λ_{fg} . This result is new and it justifies the inclusion of lift in the calculus we consider as a construct that increases its expressive power.³

More concretely, following Felleisen’s work on the expressive power of programming languages (Felleisen 1991), we prove that there does not exist a map ϕ from λ_{cc} to λ_{cc}^- , a restricted version of λ_{cc} where lift has been removed, such that:

- ϕ preserves program-ness, i.e., it maps closed expressions to closed expressions
- ϕ is a homomorphism on λ_{cc}^-
- for any program e in λ_{cc} , we have that e terminates if and only if $\phi(e)$ terminates.

To this end, we first observe that λ_{cc}^- is a conservative restriction of λ_{cc} , as required by Felleisen’s framework, i.e.:

- the term constructors of λ_{cc}^- are a subset of the term constructors of λ_{cc}
- the phrases (expressions) of λ_{cc}^- are a subset of the phrases of λ_{cc}
- the programs (closed expressions) of λ_{cc}^- are a subset of the programs of λ_{cc}
- the semantics of λ_{cc}^- is a restriction of the semantics of λ_{cc} , i.e., the semantics of a program in λ_{cc}^- is given by the rules $(\beta.v)$, $(\text{handle}.v)$, $(\text{let}.v)$, and $(\text{handle}.c)$, where, in the absence of the lift operator, the evaluation contexts J_0 are exactly the non-capturing contexts, i.e., contexts where the hole is not guarded by a handler.

Next, let us consider the following program e in λ_{cc}

handle (handle (lift (do v)) with $\lambda x . \lambda k . \Omega$, $\lambda x . \Omega$) with $\lambda x . \lambda k . x$, $\lambda x . x$

³We mean the expressive power in a very precise sense, namely as defined by Felleisen. We only claim that lift cannot be *locally* translated away. Other, *global* translations, e.g., passing the level of freeness from operations to handlers are entirely possible.

where v is any closed value, and Ω is a closed non-terminating computation. Applying the reduction rules of λ_{cc} , we can see that e evaluates to v . Indeed, the inner, diverging, handler is skipped by the lift operator, and the outer handler handles the operation by discarding the resumption and returning the value passed to the operation.

Then, if ϕ is a map from λ_{cc} to λ_{cc}^- that preserves program-ness and is homomorphic on λ_{cc}^- , the image of e through ϕ is the following program e'

$$\text{handle } (\text{handle } (\phi(\text{lift } (\text{do } v))) \text{ with } \lambda x . \lambda k . \Omega, \lambda x . \Omega) \text{ with } \lambda x . \lambda k . x, \lambda x . x$$

Now, the (closed) expression $\phi(\text{lift } (\text{do } v))$ which is in the evaluation position in e' can either diverge, or it can evaluate to a value u , or it can evaluate to a control-stuck term of the form $J_n[\text{do } u]$ for some non-capturing context J_n and a value u . In each case, program e' diverges in λ_{cc}^- . Therefore, there does not exist a translation from λ_{cc} to λ_{cc}^- that makes it possible to locally express (let alone macro-express⁴) lift in terms of algebraic operations and deep handlers.

3 Simulation of fine-grained and context-capturing evaluation

In this section we study the relation of the two calculi defined above as evaluation theories. We establish a bisimilarity between the two semantics, which guarantees that whenever an expression evaluates to some value under one semantics it evaluates to a (related) value under the other semantics. This means, in particular, that it is impossible for any expression to compute to a value under one semantics while diverging or getting stuck under the other. To achieve this result we follow the methodology developed by [Biernacki et al. \(2025\)](#), extending it to account for the nature of the differences between the two semantics.

As is usually the case with simulation proofs, we need to address the fact that the two programs may diverge in the process of evaluation by introducing a relation between the context-capturing and fine-grained computations. To this end we introduce a relation, written $e \sim e'$, which states that the program e (notionally on the context-capturing side) is related to the program e' (notionally on the fine-grained side). This allows us to state the main simulation theorems.

LEMMA 3.1 (SIMULATION OF CONTEXT-CAPTURING EVALUATION). *If $e_1 \rightarrow_{\text{cc}}^* e'_1$ and $e_1 \sim e_2$, then $e'_1 \sim e_2$.*

LEMMA 3.2 (SIMULATION OF FINE-GRAINED EVALUATION). *If $e_2 \rightarrow_{\text{fg}}^* e'_2$ and $e_1 \sim e_2$, then there exists e'_1 such that $e'_1 \sim e'_2$ and $e_1 \rightarrow_{\text{cc}}^* e'_1$.*

Moreover, the simulation relation is reflexive, and is defined in such a way that if one of the arguments is a normal form (i.e., a value, a control-stuck expression or an open-stuck expression), the other argument can reduce to a matching shape. Together, this means that we can consider the two semantics to define the same partial function.

3.1 The similarity relation

In the definition of the similarity relation, we follow our work on simulation between call-by-value and call-by-name evaluation strategies in lambda calculus ([Biernacki et al. 2025](#)). The approach is to define congruence relations on our syntactic categories, expressions and values,

⁴For macro-expressibility, the translation function ϕ is additionally required to be defined compositionally on the expression being eliminated, in this case, the lift expression ([Felleisen 1991](#)).

$$\begin{array}{c}
715 \quad \text{handle}([\], h, r) = r \\
716 \\
717 \quad \text{handle}(\text{let } x = T \text{ in } e, h, r) = \text{handle}(T, h, \lambda x. \text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r) \\
718 \quad \text{handle}(\text{lift } T, h, r) = \text{let } x = T \text{ in } r \ x \\
719 \\
720 \quad \frac{v \sim_v v'}{\text{return } v \sim_e \text{return } v'} \quad \frac{a \sim_e a' \quad e \sim_e e'}{\text{let } x = a \text{ in } e \sim_e \text{let } x = a' \text{ in } e'} \quad \frac{e \sim_e e'}{\text{lift } e \sim_e \text{lift } e'} \\
721 \\
722 \\
723 \quad \frac{u \sim_v u' \quad v \sim_v v'}{u \ v \sim_e u' \ v'} \quad \frac{v \sim_v v'}{\text{do } v \sim_e \text{do } v'} \quad \frac{e \sim_e e' \quad h \sim_v h' \quad r \sim_v r'}{\text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r \sim_e \text{handle } e' \text{ with } h', r'} \\
724 \\
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727 \quad \frac{}{x \sim_v x} \quad \frac{e \sim_e e'}{\lambda x. e \sim_v \lambda x. e'} \quad \frac{R \sim_h -, r'}{\lambda x. R[\text{return } x] \sim_v r'} \\
728 \\
729 \\
730 \quad \frac{J_0 \sim_R T_0 \quad h \sim_v h' \quad r \sim_v r'}{\text{handle } J_0 \text{ with } h, r \sim_h h', \text{handle}(T_0, h', r')} \quad \frac{}{[\] \sim_R [\]} \quad \frac{J \sim_R T}{\text{lift } J \sim_R \text{lift } T} \\
731 \\
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734 \quad \frac{J \sim_R T \quad e \sim_e e'}{\text{let } x = J \text{ in } e \sim_R \text{let } x = T \text{ in } e'} \quad \frac{R \sim_h -, r' \quad J \sim_R T'}{R[\text{lift } J] \sim_R \text{let } x = T' \text{ in } r'} \\
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\end{array}$$

Fig. 6. The action of a handler on a resumption and the main part of the similarity relation. The four relations (\sim_e , \sim_v , \sim_h and \sim_R) are mutually inductively defined.

and extend them with rules that account for discrepancies that may arise between the two semantics. The core part of the relation is presented in Figure 6. As advertised before, it turns out that in our case there is only one source of such a discrepancy: the resumptions captured by a handler may differ quite significantly. Thus, the relation on expressions, \sim_e , contains only congruence rules, while the relation on values, \sim_v , comprises the two congruence rules and a rule that relates resumptions.

On the context-capturing side (left), a resumption is always of the form $\lambda x. R[x]$, which the rule enforces, while on the fine-grained side (right) any value may be a resumption, since the semantics simply uses the return clause of the handler in this role. The rule then uses an auxiliary relation, \sim_h , to relate the captured context to the value and some fine-grained handler, which is no longer present in the resumption.

Thus, the \sim_h relates a resumption (i.e., a 0-free context J wrapped within a handler h, r) to a pair of a handler h' and a value. The sole rule of its definition posits that the fine-grained handler is related to the handler part of the captured resumption (i.e., $h \sim_v h'$), and that there is a 0-indexed fine-grained resumption T that is related to the 0-free context J , and a value r' related to the return clause of the handler r . Then, the captured resumption is related to the result of *propagating* the handler h', r' across the resumption T . This function is also presented in Figure 6, and amounts to exhaustively applying contraction rules (`handle.let`) and (`handle.lift`) at the outside of the resumption. This leaves us needing to connect n -free contexts on the context-capturing side to n -indexed resumptions on the fine-grained side.

766 The definition of that relation, written \sim_R , proceeds by following the shared structure
 767 of n -free contexts and n -indexed resumptions: this accounts for empty contexts, `let` and `lift`
 768 expressions that are not matched to a handler. To account for the handlers, which may occur
 769 on the context-capturing side but not on the fine-grained one, we notice that any handler in an
 770 n -free contexts needs to be matched to a `lift` expression, with a 0-free context between them.
 771 Thus, we can treat that final kind of an n -free context as a resumption with a `lift` and another
 772 n -free context plugged inside. This allows us to reuse the relation between resumptions
 773 and values, \sim_h , to account for the outer part of the context, and the relation between the
 774 contexts for the inner part, wrapping the matching resumption in a `let` expression on the
 775 fine-grained side to account for the outer, lifted resumption. Conceptually, one can consider
 776 this an encoding of a fact that on the fine-grained side there *used to be* a context that matched
 777 the context-capturing resumption precisely, but that it was reduced down to a value, which is
 778 all that remains of it.

780 These four mutually inductively defined relations account for all the discrepancies that
 781 can be encountered within the values of our two semantics; however, *during* the process of
 782 evaluation, some additional differences may occur. This is in line with the observations of
 783 Biernacki et al. (2025) when working with small-step semantics. To this end, we introduce
 784 additional relations linking redexes, evaluation contexts and decompositions of the two
 785 semantics, as well as the top-level similarity definition. These are presented in Figure 7.

787 The first of our relations, written \sim_E , links context-capturing evaluation contexts to their
 788 fine-grained counterparts. This is achieved by considering two cases: a context-capturing
 789 evaluation context is either an n -free context for some n , or it has the innermost resumption
 790 (a handler wrapped around a 0-free context) within an evaluation context. In the former case
 791 we can use the relation \sim_R linking the n -free context to a fine-grained resumption (which
 792 can itself be viewed as a T-indexed fine-grained evaluation context). In the latter case, we
 793 can relate our context to an evaluation context with a `handle` construct inside, provided the
 794 handler matches our resumption (via the \sim_h relation), with a recursive call for the remaining
 795 parts of the evaluation context.

797 The second relation connects *redexes*, i.e., left-hand-sides of contraction rules in both
 798 semantics. Since some of the fine-grained contractions may only occur in T-indexed contexts,
 799 we index the relation on redexes as well, writing \sim_r^k for a relation on redexes indexed
 800 with kind k . As most of the context-capturing contraction rules are mirrored in the fine-
 801 grained semantics, the bulk of the relation is structural, although do note that we relate any
 802 applications of related functions to related arguments—including matching free variables in
 803 the function positions. The only interesting rule concerns the redex of the rule (`handle.c`),
 804 i.e., an operation within a matching resumption. We relate this redex to a (`handle.do`) redex
 805 on the fine-grained side, utilising our relation on resumptions, \sim_h , to relate the resumption
 806 on the context-capturing side to the handler and return clause on the fine-grained side.
 807 Intuitively, this means that on the fine-grained side there *used to be* a context that matched
 808 the context-capturing 0-free context that mediates between operation and the handler, but
 809 that this context was reduced by the (`handle.let`) reductions (as used by the `handle` function)
 810 to the current return clause of the fine-grained handler.

812 The final complex relation of Figure 7 is the relation on *decompositions*, written \sim_d . Both
 813 semantics have three kinds of possible decompositions: a complete program is either a
 814 value, a *control-stuck* program (i.e., a `do` operation without a matching handler) or a redex
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\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{J_n \sim_R T_n}{J_n \sim_E T_n} \qquad \frac{R \sim_h h, r \quad K \sim_E E}{K[R] \sim_E E[\text{handle } [] \text{ with } h, r]} \\
\frac{u \sim_v u' \quad v \sim_v v'}{u v \sim_r^k u' v'} \qquad \frac{v \sim_v v' \quad e \sim_e e'}{\text{let } x = \text{return } v \text{ in } e \sim_r^\top \text{let } x = \text{return } v' \text{ in } e'} \\
\frac{v \sim_v v'}{\text{lift return } v \sim_r^\top \text{lift return } v'} \qquad \frac{v \sim_v v' \quad h \sim_v h' \quad r \sim_v r'}{\text{handle return } v \text{ with } h, r \sim_r^k \text{handle return } v' \text{ with } h', r'} \\
\frac{v \sim_v v' \quad h \sim_v h' \quad r \sim_v r' \quad J_0 \sim_R T_0}{\text{handle } J_0[\text{do } v] \text{ with } h, r \sim_r^k \text{handle do } v' \text{ with } h', \text{handle}(T_0, h', r')} \\
\frac{v \sim_v v' \quad R \sim_h h, r}{R[\text{do } v] \sim_r^k \text{handle do } v' \text{ with } h, r} \text{ (ALT)} \\
\frac{v \sim_v v'}{\text{return } v \sim_d \text{return } v'} \qquad \frac{v \sim_v v' \quad J_n \sim_R T_n}{J_n[\text{do } v] \sim_d T_n[\text{do } v']} \qquad \frac{e \sim_r^k e' \quad K \sim_E E_k}{K[e] \sim_d E_k[e']} \\
\frac{v \sim_v v' \quad R \sim_h -, u \quad K \sim_E E}{K[R[\text{return } v]] \sim_d E[u v']} \qquad \frac{v \sim_v v' \quad R \sim_h -, u \quad K \sim_E E_\top}{K[R[\text{lift return } v]] \sim_d E_\top[\text{let } x = \text{return } v' \text{ in } u x]} \\
\frac{e_2 \rightarrow_{\text{fg}}^* e'_2 \quad e_1 \sim_d e'_2}{e_1 \sim e_2}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 7. The remaining part of the similarity relation. We have relations on evaluation contexts (\sim_E), redexes (\sim_r^k , indexed with the kind of fine-grained context where the redex is contractible), decompositions (\sim_d) and the top-level relation (\sim).

within a matching evaluation context (since it causes no difficulties, we treat open-stuck programs together with actual redexes). The first two rules encompass the former two cases: related values are related decompositions, and operations with related arguments in related non-handling contexts are related. The latter three rules all concern redexes in contexts: the first of these is the standard case, where the two redexes and evaluation contexts match directly. The latter two, on the other hand, account for the differences between the two semantics. Firstly, we need to account for the context-capturing side *calling* a reified resumption: this plugs the captured resumption with a value, leading to a number of possible redexes, while on the fine-grained side there is no natural reduction to perform. Thus, we allow any resumption plugged with a value to relate to an application of the matching return clause to a matching value. Conversely, a resumption plugged with a lift v redex and without any further handlers may not match a lift operation on the fine-grained side, but a let expression where the resumption has been reduced by the handle function, with the let expression produced by the (handle.lift) reduction. Finally, the top-level relation \sim is defined by allowing the fine-grained

868 side any reductions to “catch up” with the decomposition of the context-capturing side of the
 869 relation.
 870

871 3.2 Proving the simulations

872 With the similarity relation defined, we can focus on proving that each semantics can simulate
 873 the other one. We begin with establishing some immediate properties of the structural
 874 relations, including reflexivity and closure under related substitutions. The former will be
 875 necessary to establish the starting point of the simulation, while the latter allows us to account
 876 for β -reductions.
 877

878
 879 LEMMA 3.3 (REFLEXIVITY OF SIMILARITY). *The similarity relations \sim_e and \sim_v are reflexive.*

880
 881 PROOF. Reflexivity of both relations is immediate by mutual induction on the structure of
 882 expressions and values. \square
 883

884 LEMMA 3.4. *The similarity relations \sim_e , \sim_v , \sim_h and \sim_R are closed under \sim_v -related
 885 substitutions, i.e., if ρ and ρ' are simultaneous substitutions such that $\rho(x) \sim_v \rho'(x)$ for each
 886 variable in their shared domain and $e \sim_e e'$ (respectively, $v \sim_v v'$, etc.), then $\rho^*(e) \sim_e \rho'^*(e')$
 887 (respectively, $\rho^*(v) \sim_v \rho'^*(v')$, etc.)*
 888

889 PROOF. The proof follows immediately via mutual induction over the structure of the
 890 similarity relations. \square
 891

892 With these preliminaries out of the way, we turn to properties more directly tied to the
 893 simulation, beginning with tying the structural similarity relation to the top-level similarity.
 894

895 LEMMA 3.5. *If $e \sim_e e'$ and $K \sim_E E$ then $K[e] \sim E[e']$.*

896
 897 PROOF. The proof proceeds by induction on the structural relatedness of e and e' , with
 898 inversion on the relatedness of the evaluation contexts when intermediate values are en-
 899 countered. In cases where the context-capturing side reaches a decomposition it is relatively
 900 straightforward to show that so does the fine-grained side. Where both sides can extend
 901 an evaluation context (either where a handle expression is encountered, or because the
 902 kind of E' is T) the proof follows by the induction hypothesis with appropriately extended
 903 contexts. Finally, where E' starts with a handler and a let or lift expression is encountered,
 904 the fine-grained side needs to perform some computation (using (handle.let) or (handle.lift)
 905 rules), which it is allowed to by the definition of similarity. Thus, we can reach a state with
 906 the appropriate sub-expression in an evaluation position and the two evaluation contexts
 907 (extended on the context-capturing side and transformed by the reduction on the fine-grained
 908 side) remain related, allowing us to finish by induction hypothesis. \square
 909
 910

911 This is the crucial lemma that ensures that any decomposition on the context-capturing
 912 side can be caught up with by the fine-grained side of the simulation. It is used heavily in both
 913 directions of the proof, and gives us reflexivity of the main similarity relation as a simple
 914 corollary (since empty contexts are related).
 915

916 COROLLARY 3.6. *The similarity relation \sim is reflexive.*
 917
 918

919 *From context-capturing to fine-grained semantics.* We now reach the part of the proof that
 920 is specific to the context-capturing semantics. We begin by proving that we can reduce the
 921 context-capturing side of two related decompositions.

922
 923 LEMMA 3.7. *If $e_1 \sim_d e_2$ and $e_1 \rightarrow_{cc} e'_1$, then $e'_1 \sim e_2$.*

924 PROOF. We proceed by case analysis on the similarity and reduction relations. The
 925 interesting case is when the contraction happens within a resumption plugged with a value,
 926 which is related to an application within a context. In that case we need to consider how
 927 the context captured by the resumption was formed. If it was empty, the reduction on the
 928 context-capturing side is $(\text{handle}.v)$, and the fine-grained side already matches the reduct (as
 929 two matching applications). If, on the other hand, the context was non-empty, we can consider
 930 its innermost constructor to learn about the structure of the value in the function position on
 931 the fine-grained side. This can then reduce (as allowed by the definition of similarity), and
 932 reach a matching state. The remaining cases simply proceed in lock-step. \square

933
 934 With the lemma above proved, it is a simple consequence that similarity is closed under
 935 reduction on the left-hand side, i.e., Lemma 3.1.

936
 937 PROOF OF LEMMA 3.1. We proceed first by induction on the sequence of context-capturing
 938 steps and within, by virtue of similarity being closed under backwards evaluation on the
 939 fine-grained side. The latter is immediate from its definition. \square

940
 941 Now we only need to account for the normal forms of the context-capturing semantics, i.e.,
 942 values, control-stuck programs and open-stuck programs. The connection is established by
 943 the following lemma.

944
 945 LEMMA 3.8. *Context-capturing normal forms are only related as decompositions to*
 946 *matching normal forms:*

- 947 • *if $\text{return } v \sim_d e$, then there exists v' such that $e = \text{return } v'$ and $v \sim_v v'$;*
- 948 • *if $J_n[\text{do } v] \sim_d e$, then there exist T_n and v' such that $e = T_n[\text{do } v']$, $v \sim_v v'$ and*
 949 *$J_n \sim_R T_n$;*
- 950 • *if $K[x v] \sim_d e$, then there exist E and v' such that $e = E[x v']$, $v \sim_v v'$ and $K \sim_E E$.*

951
 952 PROOF. This is an easy corollary of the uniqueness of decomposition. \square

953
 954 Thus, as a corollary, we obtain our simulation theorem.

955
 956 THEOREM 3.9. *If a program e evaluates to a normal form e' using the context-capturing*
 957 *semantics, i.e., $e \rightarrow_{cc}^* e' \nrightarrow_{cc}$, then e evaluates to a normal form of the same kind using*
 958 *the fine-grained semantics, i.e., there exists e'' such that $e \rightarrow_{fg}^* e'' \nrightarrow_{fg}$. In particular, if*
 959 *$e' = \text{return } v'$ for some value v' , then $e'' = \text{return } v''$ for some value v'' .*

960
 961 *From fine-grained to context-capturing semantics.* We now consider the reverse direction of
 962 the simulation. While the broad structure of the proof remains the same, there are some new
 963 complications. The most important of these is that due to the η -like expansion that occurs
 964 when the context-capturing semantics reifies a captured resumption, a $(\beta.v)$ redex on the
 965 fine-grained side may require a large number of steps on the context-capturing side. This
 966 occurs due to a chain of nested resumptions, where a return clause of the handler in the first
 967 resumption is itself a reified resumption—since this pattern can continue indefinitely, we
 968 need an inductive argument for why they may always reduce.

969

LEMMA 3.10. *The following propositions hold:*

- if $u \sim_v u'$, $v \sim_v v'$, $K \sim_E E$ and $E[u' v'] \rightarrow_{\text{fg}} e'$, then there exists e such that $K[u v] \rightarrow_{\text{cc}}^* e$ and $e \sim e'$;
- if $R \sim_h -, r'$, $v \sim_v v'$, $K \sim_E E$ and $E[r' v'] \rightarrow_{\text{fg}} e'$, then there exists e such that $K[R[\text{return } v]] \rightarrow_{\text{cc}}^* e$ and $e \sim e'$.

PROOF. By mutual induction on the structure of the relations \sim_v and \sim_h . In the former case, either the two related values are lambda-abstractions with related bodies, in which case the context-capturing semantics can simply reduce and match the fine-grained result, or it is a reified resumption, in which case it can reduce to plug the resumption with its argument and use the induction hypothesis for the second part of the lemma.

In the second part of the lemma we need to consider the context captured by the resumption. If it is non-empty we have a non-trivial redex, but we also learn the shape of the fine-grained value in the function position. Thus, we can reduce on the context-capturing side and match the fine-grained reduct. If the captured context was empty, on the other hand, the context-capturing side proceeds by the rule (`handle.v`) to reach an application, at which point we can use the inductive hypothesis for the first part of the lemma. This recursive structure highlights the shape of the chain of resumptions whose handlers' return clauses are themselves reified resumptions, as described above. \square

With the main technical hurdle dispatched, we continue in a pattern mirroring the other direction of the simulation, albeit more explicit, since the simulation relation is not closed under backwards context-capturing evaluation.

LEMMA 3.11. *If $e_1 \sim_d e_2$ and $e_2 \rightarrow_{\text{fg}} e'_2$, then there exists e'_1 such that $e_1 \rightarrow_{\text{cc}}^* e'_1$ and $e'_1 \sim e'_2$.*

PROOF. As in the other direction of the simulation, the proof proceeds by cases on the similarity as decompositions and evaluation. The only nontrivial case is the reduction of the application, which is encountered twice and handled via the two cases of the previous lemma. \square

We can now obtain Lemma 3.2 by a simple induction, using the fact that fine-grained evaluation is deterministic. The latter property follows trivially from uniqueness of decomposition.

As before we now need to consider the normal forms, this time on the fine-grained side of the similarity relation. The cases for values and control-stuck programs are analogous to the other direction of the simulation; the open-stuck programs, however, may need further reduction on the context-capturing side, due to the resumption nesting described above. Thus, we get the following lemma:

LEMMA 3.12. *Fine-grained normal forms are only related as decompositions to matching normal forms (up to additional evaluation for open-stuck programs):*

- if $e \sim_d \text{return } v'$, then there exists v such that $e = \text{return } v$ and $v \sim_v v'$;
- if $e \sim_d R_n[\text{do } v']$, then there exist J_n and v such that $e = J_n[\text{do } v]$, $v \sim_v v'$ and $J_n \sim_R R_n$;
- if $e \sim_d E[x v]$, then there exist E' and v' such that $e \rightarrow_{\text{cc}}^* E'[x v']$, $v \sim_v v'$ and $E \sim_E E'$.

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$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{x \Rightarrow_v x} \text{S-VAR} \qquad \frac{e \Rightarrow_e e'}{\lambda x. e \Rightarrow_v \lambda x. e'} \text{S-LAM} \\
\frac{v \Rightarrow_v v'}{\text{return } v \Rightarrow_e \text{return } v'} \text{S-RET} \\
\frac{}{\text{let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Rightarrow \text{let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2} \text{NL-LET} \qquad \frac{}{\text{let } x = \text{return } v_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Rightarrow e_2[v_1/x]} \text{NL-RED} \\
\frac{e_1 \Rightarrow_e e'_1 \quad e_2 \Rightarrow_e e'_2 \quad \text{let } x = e'_1 \text{ in } e'_2 \Rightarrow e}{\text{let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Rightarrow_e e} \text{S-LET} \\
\frac{}{v_1 v_2 \Rightarrow_v v_1 v_2} \text{NA-APP} \qquad \frac{}{(\lambda x. e) v_2 \Rightarrow_e [v_2/x]} \text{NA-RED} \\
\frac{v_1 \Rightarrow_v v'_1 \quad v_2 \Rightarrow_v v'_2 \quad v'_1 v'_2 \Rightarrow_e e}{v_1 v_2 \Rightarrow_v e} \text{S-APP}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 8. Definition of the super-parallel reduction \Rightarrow_e and \Rightarrow_v for the pure fragment of the calculus.

PROOF. The former two cases are an easy corollary of the unique decomposition property. The latter requires inductive reasoning analogous to Lemma 3.10. \square

Again we obtain the simulation theorem as a simple corollary.

THEOREM 3.13. *If a program e evaluates to a normal form e' using the context-capturing semantics, i.e., $e \rightarrow_{\text{fg}}^* e' \dashv\vdash_{\text{fg}}$, then e evaluates to a normal form of the same kind using the fine-grained semantics, i.e., there exists e'' such that $e \rightarrow_{\text{cc}}^* e'' \dashv\vdash_{\text{cc}}$. In particular, if $e' = \text{return } v'$ for some value v' , then $e'' = \text{return } v''$ for some value v'' .*

Thus, we have established that the two formats of semantics are equivalent as evaluation functions and precisely characterised the possible differences in the shape of the values and expressions that the two semantics produce. With our choice of semantics thus justified with respect to the commonly used format, we proceed to study the fine-grained contractions as a reduction theory.

4 Confluence of multi-step fine-grained reduction

In this section we present a proof sketch of one of the most fundamental properties of the reduction relation $\rightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}$ one expects, namely the confluence of the reduction relation or the Church-Rosser theorem (Barendregt 1985), expressed as the following diamond property for $\rightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^*$:

THEOREM 4.1 (CONFLUENCE). *If $e \rightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^* e_1$ and $e \rightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^* e_2$, then there exists a term e' , such that $e_1 \rightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^* e'$ and $e_2 \rightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^* e'$.*

We prove this theorem using a technique of *super-parallel reductions* and *complete super developments* (Aczel 1978; McKinna 2022; McKinna and Pollack 1999; Takahashi 1995; van

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$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{v \Rightarrow_v v'}{\text{do } v \Rightarrow_e \text{do } v'} \text{ S-DO} \\
\\
\frac{}{\text{lift } e \Rightarrow \text{lift } e} \text{ NL-LIFT} \qquad \frac{}{\text{lift } (\text{return } v) \Rightarrow \text{return } v} \text{ NL-RED} \\
\\
\frac{e \Rightarrow_e e' \quad \text{lift } e' \Rightarrow e''}{\text{lift } e \Rightarrow_e e''} \text{ S-LIFT} \\
\\
\frac{}{\text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r \Rightarrow \text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r} \text{ NH-HANDLE} \\
\\
\frac{r v \Rightarrow e}{\text{handle } (\text{return } v) \text{ with } h, r \Rightarrow e} \text{ NH-RET} \\
\\
\frac{x \notin \text{FV}(h, r)}{\text{handle } (\text{let } x = a \text{ in } e) \text{ with } h, r \Rightarrow \text{handle } a \text{ with } h, \lambda x. \text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r} \text{ NH-LET} \\
\\
\frac{r x \Rightarrow e_1 \quad \text{let } x = e \text{ in } e_1 \Rightarrow e_2 \quad x \notin \text{FV}(r)}{\text{handle } (\text{lift } e) \text{ with } h, r \Rightarrow e_2} \text{ NH-LIFT} \\
\\
\frac{x \notin \text{FV}(r)}{\text{handle } (\text{do } v) \text{ with } h, r \Rightarrow \text{let } x = h v \text{ in } x r} \text{ NH-LET} \\
\\
\frac{e_1 \Rightarrow_e e_2 \quad h_1 \Rightarrow_v h_2 \quad r_1 \Rightarrow_v r_2 \quad \text{handle } e_2 \text{ with } h_2, r_2 \Rightarrow e}{\text{handle } e_1 \text{ with } h_1, r_1 \Rightarrow_e e} \text{ S-HANDLE}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 9. Definition of the super-parallel reduction \Rightarrow_e for the effectful fragment of the calculus.

Raamsdonk 1993) that is a simplification of the classic proof method by *parallel reductions* due to Tait and Martin-Löf (Barendregt 1985). The idea is to define a super-parallel reduction relation \Rightarrow_e on expressions (along with a super-parallel reduction relation \Rightarrow_v on values, with analogous properties), such that $\longrightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{ig}}}^*$ and \Rightarrow_e^* coincide, and therefore, to establish the confluence of $\longrightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{ig}}}$, it suffices to show that \Rightarrow_e satisfies the diamond property, which we do using Takahashi's triangles (Takahashi 1995).

4.1 Super-parallel reductions

In Figure 8, we present the rules defining \Rightarrow_e and \Rightarrow_v for the pure fragment of the calculus. The idea is to contract, in parallel, all, some or none of the redexes present in an expression or a value. To this end, for each construct that can be eliminated by one or more reduction rules, we introduce an auxiliary relation \Rightarrow that non-deterministically applies the reduction rules or leaves the term intact, i.e., \Rightarrow is a reflexive closure of the contraction relation.

The remaining redexes are treated along similar lines. In Figure 9 we present the rules for the effectful fragment of the calculus. Two rules stand out: NH-RET and NH-LIFT. As we explain

1123 in the next section, these two rules require additional reductions, as prescribed by the premises
 1124 of the rules, in order to make it possible to resolve critical pairs present in expressions
 1125 of the form $\text{handle } (\text{let } x = \text{return } v \text{ in } e)$ with h, r and $\text{handle } (\text{lift } (\text{return } v))$ with h, r , when
 1126 proving the diamond property of \Rightarrow_e .

1127 The following lemma gathers some of the useful properties of \Rightarrow_e (\Rightarrow_v satisfies the
 1128 analogous properties).
 1129

1130 **LEMMA 4.2.** *For any expressions e and e' , and values v and v' , we have:*

- 1131 (1) $e \Rightarrow_e e$.
- 1132 (2) If $e \longrightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}} e'$, then $e \Rightarrow_e e'$.
- 1133 (3) If $e \Rightarrow_e e'$, then $e \longrightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^* e'$.
- 1134 (4) If $e \Rightarrow_e e'$ and $v \Rightarrow_v v'$, then $e[v/x] \Rightarrow_e e'[v'/x]$ for any variable x .

1136 This lemma, in each case, is proved by straightforward induction (mutually inductively
 1137 with the corresponding statements for \Rightarrow_v). It implies that $\longrightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^*$ and \Rightarrow_e^* coincide, and it
 1138 establishes the substitutivity property of \Rightarrow_e that plays an important role in the proof of the
 1139 diamond property for \Rightarrow_e .
 1140

1141 4.2 Complete super developments and the triangle lemma

1142 As for the proof of the diamond property of \Rightarrow_e , we take advantage of the notion of a
 1143 complete super development of an expression (value), which is a *deterministic* relation \Rightarrow_e^c
 1144 (\Rightarrow_v^c) that simultaneously and eagerly contracts (most of) redexes existing in a term as well as
 1145 those introduced by the rules such as NL-RED. More precisely, \Rightarrow_e^c is a subrelation of \Rightarrow_e ,
 1146 obtained from \Rightarrow_e by restricting all of the non-reducing non-deterministic \Rightarrow -rules NL-LET,
 1147 NA-APP, NL-LIFT, and NH-HANDLE, so that these rules are not allowed to introduce a top-level
 1148 redex—such a redex has to be contracted. For example, in NL-LET, e_1 is not allowed to have
 1149 the form $\text{return } v$ —such a let expression has to be reduced by NL-RED. This subrelation of \Rightarrow
 1150 is noted \Rightarrow^c .
 1151

1152 **LEMMA 4.3.** *For any expressions e and e' , we have:*

- 1153 (1) If $e \Rightarrow^c e'$, then $e \Rightarrow e'$.
- 1154 (2) If $e \Rightarrow_e^c e'$, then $e \Rightarrow_e e'$.
- 1155 (3) \Rightarrow^c and \Rightarrow_e^c are deterministic.
- 1156 (4) \Rightarrow_e^c is total.

1157 Since the relation \Rightarrow_e^c contracts at least as many redexes as \Rightarrow_e , we are in a position to prove
 1158 the *triangle lemma* of Takahashi (1995). The following lemmas are the central ingredient in
 1159 the proof of the triangle lemma (Lemma 4.8), and their proofs determine the actual definition
 1160 of the relation \Rightarrow , and, therefore, of \Rightarrow_e . Below we state one such lemma for each of the
 1161 constructs that can introduce a redex, i.e., for application, let-expression, lift-expression,
 1162 and handle-expression, and we present the most instructive fragments of the proof for the
 1163 handle-construct that deal with the only two possible critical pairs in the calculus and justify
 1164 the shape of the rules NH-RET and NH-LIFT. (Lemmas 4.4 and 4.5 require the substitutivity
 1165 property of Lemma 4.2.)
 1166

1167 **LEMMA 4.4.** *If $u_1 v_1 \Rightarrow e$, $u_1 \Rightarrow_v u_2$, $v_1 \Rightarrow_v v_2$, and $u_2 v_2 \Rightarrow^c e'$, then $e \Rightarrow_e e'$.*

1168 **LEMMA 4.5.** *If $\text{let } x = a_1 \text{ in } e_1 \Rightarrow e$, $a_1 \Rightarrow_e a_2$, $e_1 \Rightarrow_e e_2$, and $\text{let } x = a_2 \text{ in } e_2 \Rightarrow^c e'$, then
 1169 $e \Rightarrow_e e'$.*
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LEMMA 4.6. *If lift $e_1 \Rightarrow e$, $e_1 \Rightarrow_e e_2$, and lift $e_2 \Rightarrow^c e'$, then $e \Rightarrow_e e'$.*

LEMMA 4.7. *If handle e_1 with $h_1, r_1 \Rightarrow e$, $e_1 \Rightarrow_e e_2$, $h_1 \Rightarrow_v h_2$, $r_1 \Rightarrow_v r_2$, and handle e_2 with $h_2, r_2 \Rightarrow^c e'$, then $e \Rightarrow_e e'$.*

PROOF. The proof is done by case analysis on handle e_1 with $h_1, r_1 \Rightarrow e$.

The case of the the NH-HANDLE-rule is not interesting and straightforward.

Let us consider the NH-LET-rule. In this case we have $e_1 = \text{let } x = e'_1 \text{ in } e''_1$, and $e = \text{handle } e'_1 \text{ with } h_1, \lambda x. \text{handle } e''_1 \text{ with } h_1, r_1$. Let us consider the case where $\text{let } x = e'_1 \text{ in } e''_1 \Rightarrow_e e''_2[v/x]$ with $e'_1 \Rightarrow_e \text{return } v$ and $e''_1 \Rightarrow_e e''_2$ (the other case, when $\text{let } x = e'_1 \text{ in } e''_1 \Rightarrow_e \text{let } x = e'_2 \text{ in } e''_2$ is less interesting). First, let us observe that $e' = \text{handle } e''_2[v/x]$ with h_2, r_2 . Second, by rules S-LAM and S-HANDLE, we have:

$$\lambda x. \text{handle } e''_1 \text{ with } h_1, r_1 \Rightarrow_v \lambda x. \text{handle } e''_2 \text{ with } h_2, r_2.$$

Since

$$(\lambda x. \text{handle } e''_1 \text{ with } h_2, r_2) v \Rightarrow e'$$

it follows that $e \Rightarrow_e e'$ by the rule S-HANDLE. This part of the proof resolves a critical pair arising from expressions of the form

$$\text{handle let } x = \text{return } v \text{ in } e \text{ with } h, r$$

and hinges on the premise of the NH-RET-rule that allows us to reduce the application of the continuation r to the value v in the last step above, which makes it possible for \Rightarrow_e to catch up with \Rightarrow_e^c .

The other critical pair occurs when $e_1 = \text{lift } e'_1$ and the rule NH-LIFT is used. In that case, $r_1 x \Rightarrow e_r$ and $\text{let } x = e'_1 \text{ in } e_r \Rightarrow e$. Let us consider the case where $\text{lift } e'_1 \Rightarrow_e \text{return } v$ with $e'_1 \Rightarrow_e \text{return } v$ (the other case, when $\text{lift } e'_1 \Rightarrow_e \text{lift } e''_1$ with $e'_1 \Rightarrow_e e''_1$, is similar and slightly less interesting). By the definition of \Rightarrow^c , we get that $r_2 v \Rightarrow^c e'$. Since \Rightarrow^c is deterministic as well as total on applications and substitutive in the argument position (if $r x \Rightarrow^c e$, then $r v \Rightarrow^c e[v/x]$, assuming $x \notin \text{FV}(r)$), it follows that $e' = e''[v/x]$, where $r_2 x \Rightarrow^c e''$. By using Lemma 4.4, we get $e_r \Rightarrow_e e''$, which makes it possible to apply Lemma 4.5 to what we have learnt, namely that $\text{let } x = e'_1 \text{ in } e_r \Rightarrow e$, $e'_1 \Rightarrow_e \text{return } v$, $e_r \Rightarrow_e e''$, and $\text{let } x = \text{return } v \text{ in } e'' \Rightarrow e''[v/x]$, and conclude that $e \Rightarrow_e e'$. This case resolves a critical pair arising from the expressions of the form

$$\text{handle (lift (return } v)) \text{ with } h, r$$

that, by reducing the inner redex first, \Rightarrow_e^c rewrites into e' such that $r' v' \Rightarrow^c e'$ (where $v \Rightarrow_v^c v'$ and $r \Rightarrow_v^c r'$). However, \Rightarrow_e can choose the outer redex, which leads to a let-expression

$$\text{let } x = \text{return } v \text{ in } e''$$

that is immediately reduced by \Rightarrow to $e''[v/x]$, which can only catch up with e' , if $r'' x \Rightarrow e''$ (where $r \Rightarrow_v r''$). This is the reason why the NH-LIFT-rule requires the two premises.

The remaining cases, given by the rules NH-RET and NH-DO, are proved along the same lines, but since they are not concerned with critical pairs, they are less telling. \square

The triangle lemma follows from Lemmas 4.4-4.7:

LEMMA 4.8. *If $e \Rightarrow_e e'$ and $e \Rightarrow_e^c e^\bullet$, then $e' \Rightarrow_e e^\bullet$.*

1225 **PROOF.** The proof is done by induction on $e \Rightarrow_e e'$ (induction on $e \Rightarrow_e^c e^\bullet$ works as well).
 1226 We show the proof only for the `S-HANDLE`-rule, as a representative case.

1227 Let us assume that $e = \text{handle } e_0 \text{ with } h_0, r_0$ and $e \Rightarrow_e e'$. Then, for some $e_1, h_1,$ and
 1228 r_1 , we have $e_0 \Rightarrow_e e_1, h_0 \Rightarrow_v h_1, r_0 \Rightarrow_v r_1$, and $\text{handle } e_1 \text{ with } h_1, r_1 \Rightarrow e'$. By $e \Rightarrow_e^c e^\bullet$,
 1229 we then also have $e_0 \Rightarrow_e^c e_0^\bullet, h_0 \Rightarrow_v^c h_0^\bullet, r_0 \Rightarrow_v^c r_0^\bullet$, and $\text{handle } e_0^\bullet \text{ with } h_0^\bullet, r_0^\bullet \Rightarrow^c e^\bullet$, for
 1230 some $e_0^\bullet, h_0^\bullet,$ and r_0^\bullet . By the induction hypothesis, we learn that $e_1 \Rightarrow_e e_0^\bullet, h_1 \Rightarrow_v h_0^\bullet,$ and
 1231 $r_1 \Rightarrow_v r_0^\bullet$. We therefore reduce the proof in this case to the task of showing $e' \Rightarrow_e e^\bullet$ from
 1232 $\text{handle } e_1 \text{ with } h_1, r_1 \Rightarrow e', e_1 \Rightarrow_e e_0^\bullet, h_1 \Rightarrow_v h_0^\bullet, r_1 \Rightarrow_v r_0^\bullet$, and $\text{handle } e_0^\bullet \text{ with } h_0^\bullet, r_0^\bullet \Rightarrow^c e^\bullet$,
 1233 which is exactly what Lemma 4.7 states.
 1234

1235 The remaining cases are treated analogously, using the appropriate lemma for each construct
 1236 (Lemmas 4.4, 4.5, and 4.6). \square

1237
 1238 As a corollary, we show that \Rightarrow_e satisfies the diamond property, which implies Theorem 4.1.

1239 **LEMMA 4.9.** *If $e \Rightarrow_e e_1$ and $e \Rightarrow_e e_2$, then there exists e^\bullet such that $e_1 \Rightarrow_e e^\bullet$ and $e_2 \Rightarrow_e e^\bullet$.*
 1240

1241 **PROOF.** Using the facts that \Rightarrow_e^c is functional, i.e., deterministic and total (Lemma 4.2), if
 1242 $e \Rightarrow_e e_1$ and $e \Rightarrow_e e_2$, we can construct two triangles given by Lemma 4.8, and compose
 1243 them into the desired diamond, such that $e_1 \Rightarrow_e e^\bullet$ and $e_2 \Rightarrow_e e^\bullet$, where e^\bullet is the unique
 1244 term such that $e \Rightarrow_e^c e^\bullet$ (where e^\bullet does not depend on e_1 or e_2). \square
 1245

1246 As a comment on the developments of this section, we would like to argue that the fact
 1247 that our definition of \Rightarrow_e is built in the spirit of *super-parallel* reductions (McKinna 2022;
 1248 van Raamsdonk 1993), rather than of the more familiar parallel reductions (Takahashi 1995)
 1249 is essential for the proof to go through. The latter reduces all the redexes that are already
 1250 present in a term under consideration and works well, e.g., when there are no critical pairs in
 1251 the calculus, as is the case, e.g., in the λ -calculus with β -reduction. In contrast, super parallel
 1252 reductions are allowed to contract more redexes, i.e., also some redexes that are created after
 1253 the subterms of a given term have been super-parallel reduced. This extra eagerness of the
 1254 super-parallel reductions seems critical for the triangle lemma to hold in our calculus. In
 1255 particular, in a parallel reduction relation we would have the following rules:
 1256

$$1257 \frac{v_1 \Rightarrow_v v'_1 \quad e_2 \Rightarrow_e e'_2}{1258 \text{let } x = \text{return } v_1 \text{ in } e_2 \Rightarrow_e e'_2[v'_1/x]} 1259$$

1260 and

$$1261 \frac{e_1 \Rightarrow_e e'_1 \quad e_2 \Rightarrow_e e'_2 \quad h \Rightarrow_v h' \quad r \Rightarrow_v r'}{1262 \text{handle let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 \text{ with } h, r \Rightarrow_e \text{handle } e'_1 \text{ with } h', (\lambda x. \text{handle } e'_2 \text{ with } h', r')} 1263$$

1264
 1265 If we now look at an expression $e = \text{handle } (\text{let } x = \text{return } v \text{ in } e_2) \text{ with } h, r$, we observe that
 1266 $e \Rightarrow_e e'_1 = \text{handle } e'_2[v'/x] \text{ with } h', r'$ —we are allowed to reduce the inner redex, but also
 1267 $e \Rightarrow_e^c e'_2 = \text{handle return } v'' \text{ with } h'', (\lambda x. \text{handle } e'_2 \text{ with } h'', r'')$ —the outer redex has to be
 1268 reduced by \Rightarrow_e^c , as dictated by the above rule for the `handle`-construct. In this case, $e'_1 \not\Rightarrow_e e'_2$,
 1269 in general.
 1270

1271 We, therefore, conjecture that our calculus requires some form of super parallel reductions
 1272 and complete super developments for the confluence proof based on parallel reductions to go
 1273 through. Moreover, the actual definition of \Rightarrow_e is not a trivial generalization of the one for the
 1274 pure λ -calculus, but it is quite subtle in the choice of which redexes have to be contracted and
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\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{a \rightarrow^w \text{return } v \quad e[v/x] \rightarrow^w e'}{\text{let } x = a \text{ in } e \rightarrow^f e'} \text{ F-LET-RET} \qquad \frac{a \rightarrow^w a'}{\text{let } x = a \text{ in } e \rightarrow^f \text{let } x = a' \text{ in } e} \text{ F-LET} \\
\frac{e \rightarrow^w \text{return } v}{\text{lift } e \rightarrow^f v} \text{ F-LIFT-RET} \qquad \frac{e \rightarrow^w e'}{\text{lift } e \rightarrow^f \text{lift } e'} \text{ F-LIFT} \qquad \frac{}{\text{return } v \rightarrow^f \text{return } v} \text{ F-RET} \\
\frac{}{u v \rightarrow^f u v} \text{ F-APP} \qquad \frac{}{\text{do } v \rightarrow^f \text{do } v} \text{ F-DO} \\
\frac{}{\text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r \rightarrow^f \text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r} \text{ F-HANDLE} \qquad \frac{e_1 \mapsto_i^* e_2 \quad e_2 \rightarrow^f e_3}{e_1 \rightarrow^w e_3} \text{ W} \\
\frac{}{(\lambda x. e) v \mapsto_i e[v/x]} \text{ H-APP} \qquad \frac{}{\text{handle return } v \text{ with } h, r \mapsto_i r v} \text{ H-RET} \\
\frac{}{\text{handle do } v \text{ with } h, r \mapsto_i \text{let } f = h v \text{ in } f r} \text{ H-DO} \\
\frac{}{\text{handle lift } e \text{ with } h, r \mapsto_i \text{let } x = e \text{ in } r x} \text{ H-LIFT} \\
\frac{}{\text{handle let } x = a \text{ in } e \text{ with } h, r \mapsto_i \text{handle } a \text{ with } h, (\lambda x. \text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r)} \text{ H-LET} \\
\frac{e \mapsto_i e'}{\text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r \mapsto_i \text{handle } e' \text{ with } h, r} \text{ H-CONG} \\
\frac{}{x \rightarrow_v^i x} \text{ I-VAR} \qquad \frac{e_1 \rightarrow^s e_2}{\lambda x. e_1 \rightarrow_v^i \lambda x. e_2} \text{ I-LAM} \qquad \frac{v_1 \rightarrow_v^i v_2}{\text{return } v_1 \rightarrow_e^i \text{return } v_2} \text{ I-RET} \\
\frac{a_1 \rightarrow_e^i a_2 \quad e_1 \rightarrow^s e_2}{\text{let } x = a_1 \text{ in } e_1 \rightarrow_e^i \text{let } x = a_2 \text{ in } e_2} \text{ I-LET} \qquad \frac{e_1 \rightarrow_e^i e_2}{\text{lift } e_1 \rightarrow_e^i \text{lift } e_2} \text{ I-LIFT} \\
\frac{v_1 \rightarrow_v^i v_2}{\text{do } v_1 \rightarrow_e^i \text{do } v_2} \text{ I-DO} \qquad \frac{u_1 \rightarrow_v^i u_2 \quad v_1 \rightarrow_v^i v_2}{u_1 v_1 \rightarrow_e^i u_2 v_2} \text{ I-APP} \\
\frac{e_1 \rightarrow^f e_2 \quad e_2 \rightarrow_e^i e_3 \quad h_1 \rightarrow_v^i h_2 \quad r_1 \rightarrow_v^i r_2}{\text{handle } e_1 \text{ with } h_1, r_1 \rightarrow_e^i \text{handle } e_3 \text{ with } h_2, r_2} \text{ I-HANDLE} \qquad \frac{e_1 \rightarrow^w e_2 \quad e_2 \rightarrow_e^i e_3}{e_1 \rightarrow^s e_3} \text{ S}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 10. Standard reduction (\rightarrow^s), internal reduction (\rightarrow_e^i)/(\rightarrow_v^i), inner reduction (\mapsto_i), frozen weak head reduction (\rightarrow^f), and weak head reduction (\rightarrow^w).

which ones can stay intact (witness, e.g., the potential redex $h v$ generated in the NH-LET-rule that does not have to be reduced eagerly).

5 Standardisation theorem

The standardisation theorem for β -reduction in the λ -calculus, in its classical form (Mitschke 1979), states that any reduction sequence that reaches a head-normal form can be separated into a head-reduction sequence that reaches a head-normal form, followed by a number of *internal* reductions. As noted by McKinna and Pollack (1999), this can be adapted to the more practically useful notion of weak-head reductions, and since the important consequences follow already from Mitschke’s semi-standardisation, or factorisation, lemma, this is the problem we focus on in this section.

To prove standardisation, we adapt the methodology developed by Takahashi (1995) and refined by McKinna and Pollack (McKinna 2022; McKinna and Pollack 1999). The crux of the idea is to use *internal parallel* reductions to describe the internal (i.e., non-weak-head) reductions of the standard sequence. In its refined form, the *standard* reduction sequences can then be defined as a composition of weak-head reduction sequences with internal-parallel reductions,⁵ and semi-standardisation simply states that any reduction sequence can be mimicked by a standard one.

While the methodology is very refined in the case of pure lambda calculus, the fact that our notion of evaluation (with which we want the weak-head reduction to coincide) is a hybrid strategy introduces new challenges. This is because the *top* contractions ($(\text{let}.v)$ and $(\text{lift}.v)$), while part of the weak-head reduction in appropriate contexts, become *frozen* if performed within a handle expression—and both *let* and *lift* constructs cease to act as evaluation contexts within *handle*. Thus, we lose a clear, structural distinction between evaluation positions, where any weak-head reductions remain weak-head, and the remaining positions, where no weak-head reduction is possible.

These considerations led us to the definitions of weak-head, frozen, internal-parallel and standard reductions presented in Figure 10. To obtain a well-behaved definition of frozen reductions we repeat McKinna’s observation that standard sequences can be *defined* as composition of weak-head and internal reductions and adapt it as a definition of weak-head sequences: these are now formed as a composition of *inner* reductions (\rightarrow_i^*), which are always allowed within a handle expression, and the frozen reductions. The latter are defined to be reflexive and encompass weak-head reduction sequences under *let*, *lift*, and those including the two *top* contractions. It is easily shown that this notion of weak-head reduction corresponds to the notion of fine-grained evaluation ($\rightarrow_{\text{fg}}^*$) defined in Section 2.

This leaves us with the definition of standard and internal-parallel reductions. These follow the recent presentation by McKinna (2022), adapted to the fine-grained call-by-value setting. Thus, we get the notions of internal-parallel reductions for both expressions (\rightarrow_e^i) and values (\rightarrow_v^i), with the definitions following the structure of terms and allowing:

- *internal* reductions for any value sub-terms;
- *standard* reductions for any expression sub-terms outside of the evaluation position;
- *internal* reductions for expression sub-terms in evaluation position of *let* and *lift*;
- *frozen* reductions followed by *internal* reductions for the evaluation position of *handle*.

⁵As a matter of fact, in the refined proof method one can use internal reductions that are sequential rather than parallel (McKinna 2022), but the definition and the proof become less concise.

1378 The last case accounts for the hybrid nature of the weak-head reduction, as discussed
 1379 above. Finally, the standard sequences are defined as composition of weak-head and internal
 1380 reductions.

1381 The crucial step in the methodology we follow is establishing transitivity of the relations
 1382 defined as above. For this, it suffices to know that standard reductions *absorb* contractions and
 1383 weak-head reductions from the right (cf. Lemma 5.5 for finer detail). This is the heart of the
 1384 argument that reductions can be appropriately reordered, and is always somewhat involved,
 1385 as internal reductions can become unblocked through the commutation of the weak-head
 1386 reduction in front of them. Most of these cases are handled in a standard way: what remains
 1387 are the frozen reductions in the evaluation position of handle, which can also get unblocked
 1388 by the following reduction. This leads us to the following four lemmas, corresponding to the
 1389 four contractions of handle.
 1390

1391 LEMMA 5.1 (HANDLING OF VALUES). *The following implications hold:*

- 1392 (1) *If $e \rightarrow^f \text{return } v$, then handle e with $h, r \rightarrow^w r v$.*
 1393 (2) *If $e \rightarrow^w \text{return } v$, then handle e with $h, r \rightarrow^w r v$.*

1395 LEMMA 5.2 (HANDLING OF EFFECTS). *The following implications hold:*

- 1396 (1) *If $e \rightarrow^f \text{do } v$, then handle e with $h, r \rightarrow^w \text{let } x = h v \text{ in } x r$.*
 1397 (2) *If $e \rightarrow^w \text{do } v$, then handle e with $h, r \rightarrow^w \text{let } x = h v \text{ in } x r$.*

1399 LEMMA 5.3 (HANDLING OF LIFTS). *The following implications hold:*

- 1400 (1) *If $e \rightarrow^f \text{lift } e'$, then handle e with $h, r \rightarrow^w \text{let } x = e' \text{ in } r x$.*
 1401 (2) *If $e \rightarrow^w \text{lift } e'$, then handle e with $h, r \rightarrow^w \text{let } x = e' \text{ in } r x$.*

1403 LEMMA 5.4 (HANDLING OF let-EXPRESSIONS). *The following implications hold:*

- 1404 (1) *If $e \rightarrow^f \text{let } x = a \text{ in } e'$, then there exists a' such that*
 1405 *handle e with $h, r \rightarrow^w \text{handle } a' \text{ with } h, \lambda x. \text{handle } e' \text{ with } h, r$ and $a' \rightarrow^f a$.*
 1406 (2) *If $e \rightarrow^w \text{let } x = a \text{ in } e'$, then there exists a' such that*
 1407 *handle e with $h, r \rightarrow^w \text{handle } a' \text{ with } h, \lambda x. \text{handle } e' \text{ with } h, r$ and $a' \rightarrow^f a$.*
 1408

1409 In the first three cases, these simply state that a frozen reduction under handle followed by
 1410 an appropriate contraction can be simulated with a weak-head reduction sequence. In the final
 1411 one, however, we separate the original reduction sequence into two parts: a reduction sequence
 1412 that exposes a let-expression, and any frozen reductions within its evaluation position. While
 1413 the former sequence can be followed with a weak-head reduction, the latter become internal
 1414 to the resulting handler when absorbed as part of the standard reduction. Note that these
 1415 lemmas correspond to some of the critical pairs in the reduction theory, which we needed
 1416 to consider in the previous section: in a sense, they provide a resolution of these critical
 1417 pairs in concrete cases that arise from evaluation. All four of these lemmas follow by routine
 1418 mutual induction on the structure of the weak-head and frozen derivations, suggesting that
 1419 our definitions fit well with the methodology we used.
 1420

1421 Having handled the unfreezing of reductions frozen within the handle expression, we
 1422 can now return to establishing transitivity of internal and standard reduction relations. We
 1423 prove, in turn, that internal reductions on expressions absorb contractions, weak-head and
 1424 frozen reductions from the right. Most of these give rise to standard reduction sequences, but
 1425 we establish more precise commutation results for *top* contractions and frozen reductions.
 1426 These allow us to establish transitivity for internal reductions on expressions, where a lack
 1427
 1428

of precision would only give us standard reduction sequence as a result. While not strictly necessary, this is a good litmus test of our definition of internal reductions for expressions. The following lemma summarizes the transitivity results.

LEMMA 5.5 (RECOMPOSITION). *For all $e_1, e_2, e_3, v_1, v_2,$ and v_3 :*

- (1) *If $e_1 \xrightarrow{e}_i e_2 \mapsto_c e_3$, then $e_1 \twoheadrightarrow^s e_3$.*
- (2) *If $e_1 \xrightarrow{e}_i e_2 \mapsto_f e_3$, then $e_1 \twoheadrightarrow^s e_3$.*
- (3) *If $e_1 \xrightarrow{e}_i e_2 \mapsto_i e_3$, then there exists e'_2 , such that $e_1 \xrightarrow{f} e'_2 \twoheadrightarrow^i_e e_3$.*
- (4) *If $e_1 \xrightarrow{e}_i e_2 \mapsto_i e_3$, then $e_1 \twoheadrightarrow^s e_3$.*
- (5) *If $e_1 \xrightarrow{e}_i e_2 \mapsto_i^* e_3$, then $e_1 \twoheadrightarrow^s e_3$.*
- (6) *If $e_1 \xrightarrow{e}_i e_2 \twoheadrightarrow^f e_3$, then there exists e'_2 , such that $e_1 \xrightarrow{f} e'_2 \twoheadrightarrow^i_e e_3$.*
- (7) *If $e_1 \xrightarrow{e}_i e_2 \twoheadrightarrow^w e_3$, then $e_1 \twoheadrightarrow^s e_3$.*
- (8) *If $e_1 \xrightarrow{e}_i e_2 \twoheadrightarrow^i_e e_3$, then $e_1 \twoheadrightarrow^i_e e_3$.*
- (9) *If $v_1 \xrightarrow{v}_i v_2 \twoheadrightarrow^i_v v_3$, then $v_1 \twoheadrightarrow^i_v v_3$.*
- (10) *If $e_1 \twoheadrightarrow^s e_2 \twoheadrightarrow^s e_3$, then $e_1 \twoheadrightarrow^s e_3$.*

With transitivity established, the semi-standardisation theorem follows.

THEOREM 5.6 (SEMI-STANDARDISATION). *If $e \xrightarrow{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^* e'$, then $e \twoheadrightarrow^s e'$.*

PROOF. Since standard reduction is reflexive and transitive, it remains to show that single-step reduction is a subrelation of standard reduction, which follows by simple induction. \square

This is, to the best of our knowledge, the first explicitly stated standardisation result for a theory of effect handlers. Having said that, a careful reading of McLaughlin's proof of the Context Lemma for ELLA (McLaughlin 2020, Chapter 6), a core calculus of the Frank programming language (Convent et al. 2020) and thus substantially different in terms of structuring and handling effects, reveals the structure of weak-head and internal reductions characteristic to standardisation.

6 Equational reasoning

The results presented thus far license the fine-grained reduction theory we have developed to be used as a foundation for an equational theory that is sound with respect to the standard context capturing semantics. To formally state this, let us define $=_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}$ as a symmetric closure of $\xrightarrow{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^*$. Let us also define the notion of observational equivalence \approx_{cc} as follows: $e_1 \approx_{\text{cc}} e_2$ (e_1 is observationally equivalent to e_2), if for all contexts C such that both $C[e_1]$ and $C[e_2]$ are closed terms, $C[e_1] \twoheadrightarrow_{\text{cc}}^* \text{return } v_1$ for some value v_1 if and only if $C[e_2] \twoheadrightarrow_{\text{cc}}^* \text{return } v_2$ for some value v_2 .⁶ Then the following theorem holds.

THEOREM 6.1 (SOUNDNESS OF FINE-GRAINED EQUATIONAL REASONING). *If $e_1 =_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}} e_2$, then $e_1 \approx_{\text{cc}} e_2$.*

PROOF. Let us assume that $e_1 =_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}} e_2$ and $C[e_1] \twoheadrightarrow_{\text{cc}}^* v_1$ (the symmetric case is proved analogously). From the former assumption, we know that $C[e_1] =_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}} C[e_2]$. From the latter assumption, we get that $C[e_1] \xrightarrow{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^* v'_1$ by the simulation of context capturing evaluation

⁶It can be shown, straightforwardly adjusting the argument from (Biernacki et al. 2020), that this notion of observational equivalence coincides with the standard one, in which termination, rather than termination to a value, is observed. Moreover, instead of \approx_{cc} , we could introduce a notion of observational equivalence based directly on the fine-grained semantics, since thanks to the simulation theorems of Section 3 the two notions coincide.

(Theorem 3.1). Therefore, we have that $C[e_2] =_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}} v'_1$, which by the confluence of $\longrightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}$ (Theorem 4.1) gives us that $C[e_2] \longrightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^* v''_2$ for some value v''_2 . Now, applying the standardisation theorem (Theorem 5.6), we deduce that $C[e_2] \longrightarrow_{\text{fg}}^* v'_1$ for some value v'_1 . Finally, by the simulation of fine-grained evaluation (Theorem 3.2), we arrive at the conclusion $C[e_2] \longrightarrow_{\text{cc}}^* v_2$ for some value v_2 . \square

It follows from Theorem 6.1 that the directed reduction theory defined as $\longrightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}$ and understood as a program optimization, as in the motivating example in Section 1, is sound.

7 Normal forms and normalization

One of the useful consequences of the introduction of a reduction theory for effect handlers is the ability to study its normal forms and normalization processes. There are two traditional applications of such results: firstly, in partial evaluation, or specialisation of programs—such as the example presented in the introduction—and as a means to determine convertibility in dependent type theories. While only the first of these is directly applicable to our current setup (due to its untyped character), we believe that the results presented below may be useful in attempts to marry effects and effect handlers with dependent types.

7.1 Normal forms

We begin by characterising normal forms of our calculus, presented in Figure 11. The normal expressions (μ) consist of either normal values (ξ) or *neutral expressions* (ν), with normal values encompassing variables and lambda-abstractions with normalized bodies. The remainder of our normal forms are the neutral expressions: expressions that are either control-stuck, i.e., containing a `do` expression unenclosed by a `handle`, or open stuck, i.e., containing an application of a variable to a (normalized) value in a (normalized) evaluation context. The distinction in the allowable contexts is achieved, by indexing them with their kind (T or H), and preventing the appearance of intermediate values (T-kinded) if there are handlers present (any H-kinded neutral expression, however, is also a T-kinded one). Note that this description is somewhat removed from a traditional separation into normal and neutral forms of terms, where the neutral class encompasses both elimination forms and variables. In our case, variables x and their eliminations $x \xi$ belong to two different classes. This is due to their distinct reduction behaviour: the term `let $x = y \nu$ in e` cannot evaluate further (although reductions within ν or e may still be allowed), while `let $x = \text{return } y$ in e` is a valid redex.⁷ We cannot extend the notion of substitutions and allow the first computation to reduce, since a substitution of certain values for y may cause effects—and in such a case the behaviour of a hypothetical term $e[y \nu/x]$ could easily differ from the original! Therefore, the `let`-bindings, `lift` and `handle` expressions that organise the computation need to be preserved if they enclose a neutral expression, but not if they enclose a value: a substitution in a value cannot turn a stuck term into a redex.

We formalize the notion that our definitions characterise normal forms by the following lemmas (note that μ and ν trivially inject into expressions, and ξ into values):

LEMMA 7.1. *The sets μ and ξ are precisely normal forms of expressions and values, respectively, with respect to fine-grained reduction $\longrightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}$, i.e.,*

⁷Such considerations are typical of call-by-value calculi in which reduction on open terms is allowed (Accattoli and Guerrieri 2016; Lassen 2005).

1531	μ	$::= \text{return } \xi \mid \nu_{\top}$	(normal expressions)
1532			
1533	ξ	$::= x \mid \lambda x. \mu$	(normal values)
1534	ν_k	$::= (k=\top) \text{ do } \xi \mid (k=\top) \text{ let } x = \nu_{\top} \text{ in } \mu \mid (k=\top) \text{ lift } \nu_{\top} \mid x \xi \mid \text{handle } \nu_H \text{ with } \xi, \xi'$	(neutral expressions)
1535			
1536			
1537			

Fig. 11. Normal forms for fine-grained reduction.

1541	$SVal \ni v$	$::= x \mid f$	(semantic values)
1542	$SFun \ni f$	$::= [x, e, \rho] \mid v- \mid -v \mid H(f, v, v')$	(semantic functions)
1543			
1544	$\rho \in SEnv \triangleq SVal^{Var}$		(environments)
1545	$SComp \ni c$	$::= [e, \rho] \mid v v'$	(closures/semantic computations)
1546			
1547	$SVal \ni i$	$::= IRet(v) \mid ILet(c, f) \mid IDo(v) \mid ILift(c)$	(intermediate values)
1548	$SCont \ni E_k$	$::= (k=\top) \square \mid (k=\top) E_{\top}[\text{let } f] \mid (k=\top) E_{\top}[\text{lift}] \mid (k=H) E[\text{handle } \nu_h \nu_r]$	(stacks)
1549			
1550			
1551	$SAns \ni a$	$::= v \mid E_{\top}[\text{do } v] \mid E[x v]$	(answers)
1552	$Conf \ni C$	$::= \langle c \rangle_E \mid \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle_A \mid \langle f, v \rangle_F \mid \langle i \rangle_K \mid \langle i, v_h, v_r \rangle_H \mid \langle i \rangle_T \mid \langle v \rangle_{\nu_{\top}}$	(configurations)
1553			
1554			
1555			

Fig. 12. Syntax instrumented for the environment-based semantics.

1557

1558

1559 (1) *Normal forms* (μ, ξ, ν) *do not reduce*;1560 (2) *Any expression* e *(respectively, value* v) *either reduces to some expression* e' *(value* $v')$ *or is a normal form* $\mu = e$ $(\xi = v)$.

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7.2 Normalization

Since the equational theory of our calculus is given through explicitly directed, confluent reductions, it is natural to compute normal forms of expressions (where they exist, as the calculus is, in general, non-terminating) through a combination of open-term evaluation and readback functions (Grégoire and Leroy 2002). We begin by presenting the normalizer as the graph of a partial function, implementable as an inductively-defined relation that corresponds to our formalization in Rocq, which in fact can be interpreted as an environment-based abstract machine. In Appendix A, in turn, we show how this abstract machine can be implemented in a general-purpose programming language, such as OCaml, and we derive from it, using the functional correspondence (Ager et al. 2003), the corresponding higher-order compositional normalizer. The definition of the first-order normalizer we present in this section follows closely the structure of the syntactic abstract machine of Section 2.3. However, since it utilises environment semantics rather than substitutions—which makes it a more realistic model of normalization, amenable to refunctionalisation of the function space comprising the values the normalizer generates and manipulates—it requires an instrumentation with some semantic artifacts that we introduce first.

<p>1582 $\llbracket - \rrbracket_v : SVal \rightarrow Val$</p> <p>1583 $\llbracket x \rrbracket_v = x$</p> <p>1584 $\llbracket f \rrbracket_v = \lambda x. \llbracket f \rrbracket_f^x$</p> <p>1585</p> <p>1586 $\llbracket - \rrbracket_f^- : SFun \times Var \rightarrow Exp$</p> <p>1587 $\llbracket [x, e, \rho] \rrbracket_f^y = ((z \mapsto \llbracket \rho(z) \rrbracket_v)[x \mapsto y])(e)$</p> <p>1588 $\llbracket v - \rrbracket_f^x = \llbracket v \rrbracket_v x$</p> <p>1589 $\llbracket -v \rrbracket_f^x = x \llbracket v \rrbracket_v$</p> <p>1590 $\llbracket H(f, v, v') \rrbracket_f^x = \text{handle } \llbracket f \rrbracket_f^x \text{ with } \llbracket v \rrbracket_v, \llbracket v' \rrbracket_v$</p> <p>1591 $\llbracket - \rrbracket_i : SVal \rightarrow Exp$</p> <p>1592 $\llbracket IRet(v) \rrbracket_i = \text{return } \llbracket v \rrbracket_v$</p> <p>1593 $\llbracket ILet(c, f) \rrbracket_i = \text{let } x = \llbracket c \rrbracket_c \text{ in } \llbracket f \rrbracket_f^x$</p> <p>1594 $\llbracket IDo(v) \rrbracket_i = \text{do } \llbracket v \rrbracket_v$</p> <p>1595 $\llbracket ILift(c) \rrbracket_i = \text{lift } \llbracket c \rrbracket_c$</p> <p>1596</p> <p>1597 $\llbracket - \rrbracket_a : SAns \rightarrow Exp$</p> <p>1598 $\llbracket v \rrbracket_a = \text{return } \llbracket v \rrbracket_v$</p> <p>1599 $\llbracket E_T[\text{do } v] \rrbracket_a = \llbracket E_T \rrbracket_E[\text{do } \llbracket v \rrbracket_v]$</p> <p>1600 $\llbracket E[x v] \rrbracket_a = \llbracket E \rrbracket_E[x \llbracket v \rrbracket_v]$</p>	<p>$\llbracket - \rrbracket_c : SComp \rightarrow Exp$</p> <p>$\llbracket [e, \rho] \rrbracket_c = (z \mapsto \llbracket \rho(z) \rrbracket_v)(e)$</p> <p>$\llbracket v v' \rrbracket_c = \llbracket v \rrbracket_v \llbracket v' \rrbracket_v$</p> <p>$\llbracket - \rrbracket_C : Conf \rightarrow Exp$</p> <p>$\llbracket \langle c \rangle \rrbracket_C = \llbracket c \rrbracket_c$</p> <p>$\llbracket \langle v_1, v_2 \rangle_A \rrbracket_C = \llbracket v_1 \rrbracket_v \llbracket v_2 \rrbracket_v$</p> <p>$\llbracket \langle f, v \rangle_F \rrbracket_C = \llbracket f \rrbracket_f^x \llbracket \llbracket v \rrbracket_v / x \rrbracket$</p> <p>$\llbracket \langle i \rangle_K \rrbracket_C = \llbracket i \rrbracket_i$</p> <p>$\llbracket \langle i, v_h, v_r \rangle_H \rrbracket_C = \text{handle } \llbracket i \rrbracket_i \text{ with } \llbracket v_h \rrbracket_v, \llbracket v_r \rrbracket_v$</p> <p>$\llbracket \langle i \rangle_T \rrbracket_C = \llbracket i \rrbracket_i$</p> <p>$\llbracket \langle v \rangle_{VT} \rrbracket_C = \llbracket v \rrbracket_v$</p> <p>$\llbracket - \rrbracket_E : SCont \rightarrow Cont$</p> <p>$\llbracket \square \rrbracket_E = \square$</p> <p>$\llbracket E_T[\text{let } f] \rrbracket_E = \llbracket E \rrbracket_E[\text{let } x = \square \text{ in } \llbracket f \rrbracket_f^x]$</p> <p>$\llbracket E_T[\text{lift}] \rrbracket_E = \llbracket E_T \rrbracket_E[\text{lift } \square]$</p> <p>$\llbracket E[\text{handle } v_h v_r] \rrbracket_E =$</p> <p>$\llbracket E \rrbracket_E[\text{handle } \square \text{ with } \llbracket v_h \rrbracket_v, \llbracket v_r \rrbracket_v]$</p>
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Fig. 13. Erasure of semantic components of the evaluator.

1611

1612 *Semantic constructs.* The necessary components of an environment-based evaluator comprise

1613 semantic values, *functions* (lambda-like values), environments, closures (computations),

1614 semantic intermediate values, stacks, and answers; these are presented in Figure 12. Note

1615 that syntactic expressions appear only as parts of the closures, and the remainder of the

1616 instrumentation is achieved through simple inductive definitions. We represent environments

1617 as total functions from variables to semantic values, with $\rho[x \mapsto v]$ standing for the

1618 environment mapping x to v and otherwise equal to ρ .⁸ For the sake of uniformity, the

1619 evaluation will operate on pairs of stacks and *configurations*, and produce an answer as a

1620 result. The correspondence with the syntactic abstract machine is rather direct: configurations

1621 E correspond to the configurations e of the syntactic abstract machine, configurations A

1622 and F correspond to configurations a (unlike the evaluator of this section, the syntactic

1623 abstract machine is assumed to operate on closed expressions, so there is no need for a special

1624 treatment of free variables), configurations K correspond to configurations k , and so on. The

1625 role of intermediate values is played by semantic intermediate values.

1626 Note that additional semantic functions and computations are present, beyond the expected

1627 closures for functions and expressions. These arise as semantic counterparts of the code that

1630 ⁸The precise implementation of the environments depends on the representation of variables, which we abstract

1631 from in this section.

1633	$V : \text{Val} \times \text{SEnv} \rightarrow \text{SVal}$	$I : \text{IVal} \times \text{SEnv} \rightarrow \text{SIVal}$
1634		
1635	$V(x, \rho) = \rho(x)$	$I(\text{return } v, \rho) = I\text{Ret}(V(v, \rho))$
1636	$V(\lambda x. e, \rho) = [x, e, \rho]$	$I(\text{let } x = e_1 \text{ in } e_2, \rho) = I\text{Let}([e_1, \rho], [x, e_2, \rho])$
1637		$I(\text{do } v, \rho) = I\text{Do}(V(v, \rho))$
1638		$I(\text{lift } e, \rho) = I\text{Lift}([v, \rho])$
1639		
1640		
1641		

Fig. 14. Interpretation of values and intermediate values.

1642
1643
1644
1645 reduction rules create, as will become apparent once we see the evaluator. They can also
1646 be thought of as semantic continuations representing the syntactic continuations that the
1647 syntactic abstract machine encodes as terms in the last three transitions from the h-mode,
1648 e.g., in the transition
1649

$$1650 \quad \langle \text{do } v \mid h \mid r \mid E \rangle_h \triangleright \langle E \mid \text{let } x = h v \text{ in } x r \rangle_k$$

1651 the right hand side encodes a computation $h v$ with a local continuation $x r$, where x is the result
1652 of the computation $h v$. In the semantic evaluator this local continuation is represented as $-v_r$,
1653 where v_r represents r . Similarly, the other two h-transitions in the syntactic abstract machine
1654 introduce local continuations which are represented as $v-$ and $H(f, v, v')$, respectively.
1655

1656 Figure 13 we present erasure functions for semantic values, functions, computations,
1657 semantic intermediate values, and configurations that map these into values or expressions,
1658 as appropriate. These can be naturally extended to the stacks (which share the structure with
1659 evaluation contexts) and answers. The erasure functions will be useful in the following, but,
1660 hopefully, they also provide a better intuition for the interpretation of the semantic constructs.
1661

1662 There are three points worth mentioning here. First, in order to translate a local continuation
1663 expressed as a functional value f , a fresh variable x denoting the formal parameter of the
1664 continuation is generated and the body of the continuation is translated with x as a parameter.
1665 This requires value closures $[y, e, \rho]$ to have their bound variable y renamed to x —a
1666 consequence of placing both the expressible values (value closures) and local continuations
1667 within the same data type. Second, translating closures $[e, \rho]$ (and $[y, e, \rho]$) away is achieved
1668 by constructing a substitution $(z \mapsto [\rho(z)]_v)$ that maps variables to syntactic values and then
1669 mapping this substitution over the body of the closure, written $(z \mapsto [\rho(z)]_v)(e)$. Third, the
1670 $\langle f, v \rangle_F$ configurations are translated by applying the translation f to the translation of v , which
1671 reflects the role of F-configurations.
1672

1673 *Evaluation.* With the necessary semantic components defined, we now turn to the definition
1674 of the evaluation and read-back functions. Since both of these are partial, we present them
1675 via their graphs, as inductively defined predicates that are functional. In this, we follow
1676 some of the spirit of Abel’s presentation of untyped normalization-by-evaluation via partial
1677 applicative structures (Abel 2013), although due to the call-by-value nature of the reduction
1678 theory and the presence of control operators the spaces defined above do not form partial
1679 applicative structures as such.
1680

1681 The evaluation, presented in Figure 15, is an abstract-machine-style big-step semantics,
1682 reminiscent of Harper *et al.*’s account of call/cc in SML (Harper *et al.* 1993). Moreover, the
1683

$$\begin{array}{c}
1684 \quad \frac{\langle l(i, \rho) \rangle_K, E \searrow a}{\langle [i, \rho] \rangle_E, E \searrow a} \qquad \frac{\langle V(v_1, \rho), V(v_2, \rho) \rangle_A, E \searrow a}{\langle [v_1 v_2, \rho] \rangle_E, E \searrow a} \\
1685 \\
1686 \\
1687 \\
1688 \quad \frac{\langle [e, \rho] \rangle_E, E[\text{handle } V(h, \rho) V(r, \rho)] \searrow a}{\langle [(\text{handle } e \text{ with } h, r), \rho] \rangle_E, E \searrow a} \qquad \frac{\langle v_1, v_2 \rangle_A, E \searrow a}{\langle v_1 v_2 \rangle_E, E \searrow a} \\
1689 \\
1690 \\
1691 \\
1692 \quad \frac{}{\langle x, v \rangle_A, E \searrow E[x v]} \qquad \frac{\langle f, v \rangle_F, E \searrow a}{\langle f, v \rangle_A, E \searrow a} \\
1693 \\
1694 \\
1695 \quad \frac{\langle [e, \rho[x \mapsto v]] \rangle_E, E \searrow a}{\langle [x, e, \rho], v \rangle_F, E \searrow a} \qquad \frac{\langle v_1, v_2 \rangle_A, E \searrow a}{\langle -v_2, v_1 \rangle_F, E \searrow a} \qquad \frac{\langle f, v \rangle_F, E[\text{handle } v_1 v_2] \searrow a}{\langle H(f, v_1, v_2), v \rangle_F, E \searrow a} \\
1696 \\
1697 \\
1698 \quad \frac{}{\langle v_1, v_2 \rangle_A, E \searrow a} \\
1699 \quad \frac{}{\langle v_1 -, v_2 \rangle_F, E \searrow a} \\
1700 \\
1701 \\
1702 \quad \frac{\langle i, v_h, v_r \rangle_H, E \searrow a}{\langle i \rangle_K, E[\text{handle } v_h v_r] \searrow a} \qquad \frac{\langle i \rangle_T, E_T \searrow a}{\langle i \rangle_K, E_T \searrow a} \\
1703 \\
1704 \\
1705 \quad \frac{\langle v_r, v \rangle_A, E \searrow a}{\langle \text{IRet}(v), v_h, v_r \rangle_H, E \searrow a} \qquad \frac{\langle c \rangle_E, E[\text{handle } v_h H(f, v_h, v_r)] \searrow a}{\langle \text{ILet}(c, f) \rangle_H, E[\text{handle } v_h v_r] \searrow a} \\
1706 \\
1707 \\
1708 \\
1709 \quad \frac{\langle \text{ILet}(v_h v, -v_r) \rangle_K, E \searrow a}{\langle \text{IDo}(v) \rangle_H, E[\text{handle } v_h v_r] \searrow a} \qquad \frac{\langle \text{ILet}(c, v_r -) \rangle_K, E \searrow a}{\langle \text{ILift}(c) \rangle_H, E[\text{handle } v_h v_r] \searrow a} \\
1710 \\
1711 \\
1712 \\
1713 \quad \frac{\langle v \rangle_{VT}, E_T \searrow a}{\langle \text{IRet}(v) \rangle_T, E_T \searrow a} \qquad \frac{\langle c \rangle_E, E_T[\text{let } f] \searrow a}{\langle \text{ILet}(c, f) \rangle_T, E_T \searrow a} \qquad \frac{}{\langle \text{IDo}(v) \rangle_T, E_T \searrow E_T[\text{do } v]} \\
1714 \\
1715 \\
1716 \quad \frac{}{\langle c \rangle_E, E_T[\text{lift}] \searrow a} \\
1717 \quad \frac{}{\langle \text{ILift}(c) \rangle_T, E_T \searrow a} \\
1718 \\
1719 \\
1720 \quad \frac{}{\langle v \rangle_{VT}, \square \searrow v} \qquad \frac{\langle f, v \rangle_F, E \searrow a}{\langle v \rangle_{VT}, E[\text{let } f] \searrow a} \qquad \frac{\langle v \rangle_{VT}, E \searrow a}{\langle v \rangle_{VT}, E[\text{lift}] \searrow a} \\
1721 \\
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1729 \quad \frac{\langle \text{ILet}(v_h v, -v_r) \rangle_K, E \searrow a}{\langle \text{IDo}(v), v_h, v_r \rangle_H, E \searrow a} \\
1730 \\
1731 \\
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\end{array}$$

Fig. 15. The evaluation judgment.

inductive rules very closely follow the transitions of the syntactic abstract machine, e.g., the rule

$$\frac{\langle \text{ILet}(v_h v, -v_r) \rangle_K, E \searrow a}{\langle \text{IDo}(v), v_h, v_r \rangle_H, E \searrow a}$$

when read bottom up can be viewed as the following transition of an abstract machine

$$\langle \text{IDo}(v), v_h, v_r \rangle_H, E \triangleright \langle \text{ILet}(v_h v, -v_r) \rangle_K, E$$

1735 which is a counterpart of the corresponding transition in the syntactic abstract machine. In
 1736 other words, the evaluator of Figure 15 has been obtained from the syntactic abstract machine
 1737 by introducing the environment, replacing purely syntactic entities with their environment-
 1738 instrumented counterparts, and replacing machine transitions with inductive rules that mimic
 1739 the transitions.

1740 The evaluation, therefore, proceeds as in the syntactic abstract machine by inspecting
 1741 the configuration and—in the case of the K- and VT-configurations—the stack. The eval
 1742 configuration (denoted by E) inspects the closure, decomposes the expression, taking
 1743 advantage of two auxiliary interpretation functions V and I shown in Figure 14, and chooses
 1744 either the continuation or application configuration. The apply configuration (A) either
 1745 recognises that the computation is open stuck, producing an appropriate answer, or continues
 1746 with the application of the function. The function-application configuration (F) proceeds
 1747 depending on the shape of the function: if it is a closure, the argument is added to the
 1748 environment, and the evaluation proceeds in the usual fashion (this step corresponds to
 1749 $(\beta.v)$ reduction). The two “application” functions apply one of the arguments to the other,
 1750 according to which one was missing. Finally, the H function reconstructs the larger context
 1751 within which its first argument can now be applied to the given value.
 1752

1753 This leaves us with the continuation configurations. The K-configuration is used to
 1754 recognize if the given semantic intermediate value i has a handler on the stack or not.
 1755 If it does, i is “handled” by the H-configuration according to the four transitions from
 1756 h-configuration in the syntactic abstract machine, which are the analogues of (handle.v),
 1757 (handle.do), (handle.let) and (handle.lift) reductions. If it does not, the T-configuration is
 1758 used to interpret i with a top-level stack E_T , again, completely in harmony with how transitions
 1759 from t-configuration in the syntactic abstract machine work. In particular, at this point a do
 1760 expression is reported as control-stuck and the answer is returned, while let and lift simply
 1761 extend the stack and return to the eval configuration. Finally, the remaining configuration
 1762 (VT) represents continuation of the evaluation when in the T-configuration a value has been
 1763 encountered: this can either lead to the final result of the computation when the stack is
 1764 empty, or the remaining two contractions: (let.v) or (lift.v).
 1765

1766 Note that the relation is obviously functional in its two arguments, thus representing a
 1767 graph of a partial function. Before turning to the read-back function and the process of full
 1768 normalization, we remark that the evaluation judgment defined above corresponds with the
 1769 weak-head reduction defined in Section 5.
 1770

1771 **LEMMA 7.2.** *If any configuration C with a stack E evaluates to an answer a, i.e., $C, E \searrow a$,
 1772 then its erasure reduces to the erasure of the answer: $[E]_E[[C]_C] \rightarrow^w [a]_a$.*

1773 **LEMMA 7.3.** *For any two configurations C_1, C_2 such that $[C_1]_C \rightarrow^w [C_2]_C$ and two stacks
 1774 E_1, E_2 such that $[E_1]_E = [E_2]_E$, the two evaluations are equivalent as partial functions, i.e.,*

- 1775 (1) *for any a_1 , if $C_1, E_1 \searrow a_1$, then $C_2, E_2 \searrow a_2$ for some a_2 such that $[a_1]_a = [a_2]_a$;*
 1776 (2) *for any a_2 , if $C_2, E_2 \searrow a_2$, then $C_1, E_1 \searrow a_1$ for some a_1 such that $[a_1]_a = [a_2]_a$.*

1777 Since any expression that cannot progress in terms of weak-head reduction is an answer, the
 1778 latter lemma leads to a simple corollary that any reduction to a weak-head normal form can be
 1779 computed (up to erasure) by the evaluator ($x \mapsto x$ represents the initial identity environment):
 1780

1781 **COROLLARY 7.4.** *For any expressions e_1, e_2 such that $e_1 \rightarrow^w e_2$ and $e_2 \not\rightarrow^w$, there exists
 1782 an answer a such that $\langle\langle e_1, x \mapsto x \rangle\rangle_E, \square \searrow a$ and $[a]_a = e_2$.*

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\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\text{RB}_v v \searrow \xi}{\text{RB}_a v \searrow \xi} \qquad \frac{\text{RB}_v v \searrow \xi \quad \text{RB}_E E[x \xi] \searrow v}{\text{RB}_a E[x v] \searrow v} \\
\\
\frac{\text{RB}_v v \searrow \xi \quad \text{RB}_E E_T[\text{do } \xi] \searrow v}{\text{RB}_a E_T[\text{do } v] \searrow v} \\
\\
\frac{}{\text{RB}_v x \searrow x} \qquad \frac{\text{RB}_f f^x \searrow \mu}{\text{RB}_v f \searrow \lambda x. \mu} \qquad \frac{\langle f, x \rangle_F, \square \searrow a \quad \text{RB}_a a \searrow \mu}{\text{RB}_f f^x \searrow \mu} \\
\\
\frac{}{\text{RB}_E \square[v] \searrow v} \qquad \frac{\text{RB}_f f^x \searrow \mu \quad \text{RB}_E E_T[\text{let } x = v \text{ in } \mu] \searrow v'}{\text{RB}_E E_T[\text{let } f][v] \searrow v'} \\
\\
\frac{\text{RB}_E E_T[\text{lift } v] \searrow v'}{\text{RB}_E E_T[\text{lift}][v] \searrow v'} \\
\\
\frac{\text{RB}_v v \searrow \xi \quad \text{RB}_v v' \searrow \xi' \quad \text{RB}_E E[\text{handle } v_H \text{ with } \xi, \xi'] \searrow v'}{\text{RB}_E E[\text{handle } v v'] [v_H] \searrow v'}
\end{array}$$

Fig. 16. The read-back judgment.

More important, from the normalization perspective, is the relationship of evaluation to general reduction. Instead of tackling this problem directly, we utilise the standardisation theorem, which helps us order the general reduction sequence. In order to state the lemmas, we first define the notions of reduction for the components of the evaluator by taking $v \rightarrow_v v' \triangleq [v]_v \rightarrow^i [v']_v$ and $f \rightarrow_f f' \triangleq [f]_f^x \rightarrow^s [f']_f^x$, and defining the notions for stacks (\rightarrow_E) and answers (\rightarrow_a) as a congruential closure over the constructors of the notions for values and functions. These definitions are straightforward as illustrated by the following two representative rules:

$$\frac{E \rightarrow_E E' \quad v \rightarrow_v v'}{E[x v] \rightarrow_a E'[x v']} \qquad \frac{E \rightarrow_E E' \quad f \rightarrow_f f'}{E[\text{let } f] \rightarrow_E E'[\text{let } f']}$$

This lets us state the properties that relate reduction and evaluation.

LEMMA 7.5. *For any configurations C_1, C_2 and stacks E_1, E_2 such that $[E_1]_E[[C_1]_C] \rightarrow^s [E_2]_E[[C_2]_C]$:*

- (1) *if $C_1, E_1 \searrow a_1$ for some a_1 , there exists a_2 such that $C_2, E_2 \searrow a_2$ and $a_1 \rightarrow_a a_2$;*
- (2) *if $C_2, E_2 \searrow a_2$ for some a_2 , there exists a_1 such that $C_1, E_1 \searrow a_1$ and $a_1 \rightarrow_a a_2$.*

Read-back. With the evaluation aspect defined, we now turn to the read-back function, whose graph is defined inductively in Figure 16. It consists of four mutually inductive predicates: reading back answers as normal forms (RB_a), semantic values as normal values (RB_v), semantic functions (with a variable name as a second parameter) as normal forms RB_f , and stacks, together with neutral expressions (RB_E). Most of the process proceeds structurally, with all the recursive evaluation in the internal structure delegated to reading

1837 back of functions—which, as expected, proceeds by applying the function to the fresh variable
 1838 (chosen to match the appropriate binder in the resulting normal form). The definition of
 1839 $\text{RB}_E E[\nu] \searrow \nu'$ is an enriched plug operation that reifies context E frame by frame and plugs
 1840 the result with a neutral expression ν yielding another neutral expression ν' . The invariant
 1841 here is that E , ν , and ν' are of the same kind, which we elide to avoid clutter.

1842 As expected, the following properties are rather simple to obtain, given the lemmas about
 1843 evaluation above.
 1844

1845 **LEMMA 7.6.** *The read-back process only performs internal reductions, i.e., for any answer*
 1846 *a and normal form μ , if $\text{RB}_a a \searrow \mu$, then $[a] \rightarrow^i \mu$.*

1847
 1848 **LEMMA 7.7.** *The read-back process is closed under reductions of answers, i.e., for any*
 1849 *answers a_1, a_2 such that $a_1 \rightarrow_a a_2$*

- 1850 (1) *if $\text{RB}_a a_1 \searrow \mu$ for some μ , then $\text{RB}_a a_2 \searrow \mu$;*
 1851 (2) *if $\text{RB}_a a_2 \searrow \mu$ for some μ , then $\text{RB}_a a_1 \searrow \mu$.*
 1852

1853 The proofs proceed by induction on the structure of the derivation of read-back, mutually
 1854 with analogous lemmas for values, functions and contexts, and utilise appropriate lemmas
 1855 about evaluation in the case for functions.

1856 Together with the standardisation theorem and the lemmas about behaviour of evaluation
 1857 with respect to standard reduction, we obtain soundness and completeness of the normalization
 1858 process.
 1859

1860 **THEOREM 7.8 (SOUNDNESS AND COMPLETENESS OF NBE).** *The (partial) normalization*
 1861 *function, defined as*

$$1862 \text{norm}(e) \searrow \mu \iff \exists a. \langle \langle e, x \mapsto x \rangle \rangle_{E, \square} \searrow a \wedge \text{RB}_a a \searrow \mu$$

1864 *is sound and complete, i.e.,*

- 1865 (1) *for any e, μ , if $\text{norm}(e) \searrow \mu$ then $e \rightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^* \mu$;*
 1866 (2) *for any e_1, e_2 if $e_1 =_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}} e_2$ and $\text{norm}(e_1) \searrow \mu$ for some μ , then $\text{norm}(e_2) \searrow \mu$.*
 1867

1868 Since $\text{norm}(\mu) \searrow \mu$, for any normal form μ , Theorem 7.8 implies that if $e \rightarrow_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}}^* \mu$ or, more
 1869 generally, $e =_{\lambda_{\text{fg}}} \mu$, then the normalization procedure will compute the normal form of e , i.e.,
 1870 $\text{norm}(e) \searrow \mu$.

1871 The partial normalizer that we obtained matches our expectations outlined in the intro-
 1872 duction. Indeed, if we extended our language (and the normalizer) with lists, the result of
 1873 normalization of the example from the introduction is the sequence of operations that we
 1874 expected to obtain.
 1875

1876 8 Related work

1877 8.1 Reduction semantics for effect handlers

1879 Operational semantics of effect handlers is typically presented as a small-step reduction
 1880 relation that either takes advantage of explicitly represented evaluation contexts and captures
 1881 resumptions at once, or it builds the resumption piece-by-piece with a helper construct that
 1882 holds a prefix of the context to be captured in search of the matching handler. In each case,
 1883 the resumption is built inside-out.
 1884

1885 The former, more global approach can be found, e.g., in Leijen’s work on Koka (Leijen
 1886 2017b), in Hillerström et al.’s work on effect handlers in the context of the Links programming
 1887

1888 language (Hillerström et al. 2020), and in a series of papers coauthored by the first and third
1889 authors revolving around the Helium programming language (Biernacki et al. 2018, 2019;
1890 Piróg et al. 2019). Such semantics is an adaptation of a classical context-sensitive reduction
1891 semantics for delimited control introduced by Felleisen et al. (Biernacka et al. 2005a) and
1892 directly implementable on a CEK-like abstract machine (Biernacka et al. 2005b; Dybvig et al.
1893 2007; Felleisen and Friedman 1987).

1894 The latter, more local approach can be found, e.g., in Bauer and Pretnar’s calculi modelling
1895 the Eff programming language (Bauer and Pretnar 2015; Kammar et al. 2013; Pretnar 2015)
1896 or in Schuster et al.’s foundations of the Effekt programming language, based on the notion of
1897 capability (Schuster et al. 2022), where the continuation is captured by unwinding the stack of
1898 a CEK-like abstract machine. Again, such semantics is an adaptation of a classical operational,
1899 based on local reduction rules, semantics for calculi with control operators (Felleisen et al.
1900 1986), first applied to delimited control by Felleisen (1988).

1901 In principle, it is relatively easy to see the correspondence between the global and local
1902 semantics of a calculus and to define one given the other one. In both cases performing the
1903 effect operation initiates the resumption capture. The fine-grained operational semantics of
1904 Section 2 is based on an entirely different principle. Here, the handler plays the leading role
1905 and the semantics of the program hinges on the reduction rules that describe the interaction
1906 of the handler with other constructs. As a consequence, the resumption is built outside-in.
1907 Altogether, this new design makes it non-trivial to establish the correctness of the semantics
1908 but, at the same time, opens new possibilities for applications. Moreover, it does not require
1909 the runtime system to search or unwind the stack or to keep track of the freeness level for
1910 contexts, otherwise critical in the presence of lift (Biernacki et al. 2018, 2019; Piróg et al.
1911 2019). This form of operational semantics is already present in the authors’ work on the
1912 control operator `shift0` (Biernacki et al. 2021).

1913 8.2 *Rewriting rules for handlers as code optimisation*

1914 Pretnar (2015) presents a set of basic equivalences for labeled handlers that are sound with
1915 respect to observational equivalence in their calculus. In his PhD dissertation (Saleh 2019),
1916 Saleh goes further and defines a set of optimisation rules for handlers that is divided into
1917 the simplification rules and handler-reduction rules (earlier works in this line include (Saleh
1918 and Schrijvers 2016) and (Pretnar et al. 2017)). The former serve as administrative rules
1919 to expose handlers, whereas the latter aim at eliminating or distributing handlers. Three of
1920 them coincide with our rules (`handle.v`), (`handle.do`), and (`handle.let`), one is dedicated
1921 to a treatment of recursive functions, which we do not need to handle explicitly, and the
1922 last one deals with pure computations. The latter rule takes advantage of a type-and-effect
1923 system – we instead work in the untyped setting. These optimisation rules were then used
1924 by Karachalias et al. (2021) in their study of efficient compilation of effect handlers, again,
1925 heavily relying on a type-and-effect system (with subtyping).

1926 None of the above works treats the optimisation rules as a reduction theory proper. In
1927 particular, no properties such as confluence or standardisation have been established before
1928 for the reduction rules that are the topic of the present work. Moreover, Saleh and Karachalias
1929 et al. only prove soundness of their reduction rules with respect to contextual equivalence,
1930 whereas we establish both their soundness and completeness with respect to the standard
1931 operational semantics.

8.3 *Confluence and Standardisation Proofs*

Our proofs of confluence and standardisation theorems follow the most recent Agda formalization of these results for the pure λ -calculus by McKinna, presented in his unpublished lecture notes (McKinna 2022). The confluence proof is based on the technique of super-parallel reductions and complete super developments (Aczel 1978; McKinna 2022; McKinna and Pollack 1999; Takahashi 1995; van Raamsdonk 1993), which is a simplification of the classic proof method by parallel reductions due to Tait and Martin-Löf (Barendregt 1985). The proof of the standardisation theorem (Mitschke 1979), in turn, is based on the methodology introduced by Takahashi (1995) and refined by McKinna and Pollack (McKinna 2022; McKinna and Pollack 1999). McLaughlin’s proof of the Context Lemma for ELLA (McLaughlin 2020, Chapter 6), a core calculus of the Frank programming language (Convent et al. 2020), takes advantage of some of the techniques characteristic to such standardisation proofs.

8.4 *Normalization by evaluation for algebraic effects*

The only result that appears to directly take up the subject of a fully normalizing procedure for a calculus with algebraic effects is due to Ahman and Staton (2013). The normalization-by-evaluation algorithm presented in that work is rather distant from ours: it relies on a (simple) type system and the grammar of terms does not include effect handlers, just algebraic operations to be interpreted at the meta level, in a residualizing monad.

Normalization by evaluation for the untyped lambda calculus has been studied in (Abel 2013; Aehlig and Joachimski 2004; Filinski and Rohde 2005). We followed Abel’s work that relies on partial applicative structures and big-step operational semantics (Harper et al. 1993; Kahn 1987). These normalizers are in the functional correspondence (Ager et al. 2003) with fully normalizing abstract machines (Biernacka et al. 2020, 2022; García-Pérez and Nogueira 2014). A read-back function was first presented as a key ingredient of a compiled fully normalizing abstract machine in (Grégoire and Leroy 2002).

9 **Conclusion and future work**

We have introduced an operational semantics for deep effect handlers based on a notion of fine-grained reduction that describes the interaction of control delimiters (handlers) with other computation formers. Based on this notion of contraction, we have developed a reduction theory, with classic properties such as confluence and standardisation—some of the earliest such results for reduction theories of effect handlers and, to the best of our knowledge, the first explicitly stated. Due to the complexities of the reduction rules and the hybrid nature of the evaluation, certain technical innovations were introduced to the classic techniques used in these proofs. We believe that they may generalise to other theories that exhibit similar complexities.

To connect our semantics to the traditional, context-capturing notion of evaluation we have established a bisimilarity between the two; thus, since our reductions are more local and finer-grained, we provide a more powerful equational theory that is nonetheless compatible with the traditional evaluators. As a further application of our semantics to partial evaluation, we have developed the first formalized normalization-by-evaluation procedure for an effect handler calculus, which can be used in program specialisation, or to establish convertibility of expressions involving handlers. These developments fill a significant gap in theoretical foundations of programming with effect handlers.

Formalization. As noted in the introduction, the bulk of the results presented above has been formalized using the Rocq interactive theorem prover. In order to aid clarity, we have used explicit variable names with a hygienic convention in play throughout the paper, where the formalization uses a functorial, intrinsically well-scoped representation (Sieczkowski and Polesiuk 2024); this, however, is clearly an adequate choice. Except for this point, the presentation follows the formalization closely, although there are cosmetic differences in the presentation of the evaluator in Section 7. We believe that our formalization effort presents additional evidence for scalability of techniques such as super-parallel reductions (in Section 4) or parallel internal reductions (in Section 5) to complex reduction theories: while we had to extend those in certain ways to account for the particular critical pairs or the fact that our weak-head reduction is a hybrid strategy, the fact that they *could* be naturally extended speaks to their robustness.

Future work. While significant theoretical properties of our calculus have been established, there are still major directions for future work. Firstly, the impact of the fine-grained semantics on the connection between effect handlers and pure lambda calculus, through a transformation to continuation-passing style, should be explored. Such a development would help ensure that the reduction rules are not just internally coherent, but tie in appropriately with a compilation process to a pure calculus. It might also shed light on whether a variant of the semantics where lift in evaluation position is always control-stuck is more natural than the current formulation. A separate area for investigation is the interplay between the fine-grained rules and shallow handlers: it is clear that in the current presentation the rules are not easily applicable to shallow handlers (Hillerström and Lindley 2018).⁹ If adaptation of the fine-grained approach to shallow handlers proves impossible, characterising and explaining such a failure could provide a valuable insight into the nature of the two varieties of control operators. Finally, our normalization algorithm could be used—in a statically-typed, terminating context—as a basis for convertibility checking, which could help guide integration of effect handlers (with type-and-effect-systems) and dependent types.

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⁹The same applies to delimited control operators, where `shift0/reset` admit fine-grained rules, while the status is unclear for `control0/prompt`.

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- 2187
- 2188
- 2189
- 2190
- 2191
- 2192
- 2193

```

2194 type 'a value =
2195   | Var of 'a
2196   | Lam of ('a option) expr
2197 and 'a expr =
2198   | Val of 'a value
2199   | App of 'a value * 'a value
2200   | Let of 'a expr * ('a option) expr
2201   | Lift of 'a expr
2202   | Do of 'a value
2203   | Hndl of 'a expr * 'a value * 'a value
2204
2205
2206 type top = |
2207 type hnd = |
2208
2209 type 'a nf =
2210   | NV of 'a nv
2211   | NC of ('a, top) nc
2212 and 'a nv =
2213   | NVar of 'a
2214   | NLam of 'a option nf
2215 and ('a, _) nc =
2216   | NDo : 'a nv -> ('a, top) nc
2217   | NApp : 'a * 'a nv -> ('a, 'b) nc
2218   | NLift : ('a, top) nc -> ('a, top) nc
2219   | NLet : ('a, top) nc * 'a option nf -> ('a, top) nc
2220   | NHndl : ('a, hnd) nc * 'a nv * 'a nv -> ('a, 'b) nc
2221
2222

```

Fig. 17. The syntax of the calculus and the normal forms as OCaml datatypes.

A Implementations of the normalizer

In this section, we discuss the implementation of the normalization algorithm of Section 7 as OCaml functions, rather than the inductively defined relation.

The syntax of the calculus, presented in Figure 17, is defined in a functorial style, with the type argument that determines the type of free variables (Bird and Paterson 1999). This allows us to ensure that terms of the calculus are well-scoped (and any operations on them preserve scope appropriately), and is in line with the Rocq formalization. However, in contrast to substitution-based approaches, we do not need to provide the syntactic renaming and substitution operations on the programs: the programs are static inputs to the evaluator. We also provide the syntax of the normal forms, following closely the presentation in Figure 11. In particular, we keep track of whether the handler is present: the empty type `top` corresponds to the index T, while another empty type, `hnd`, corresponds to the index H (and thus, to the normal form occurring under a `handle` construct).

```

2245 type 'a sval =
2246   | SVar of 'a
2247   | SFun of 'a sfun
2248 and 'a sfun =
2249   | SCl : 'b option expr * ('b, 'a) env -> 'a sfun
2250   | SAppL of 'a sval
2251   | SAppR of 'a sval
2252   | SHRet of 'a sfun * 'a sval * 'a sval
2253 and ('a, 'b) env = 'a -> 'b sval
2254
2255
2256 type 'a sclo =
2257   | CPair : 'a expr * ('a, 'b) env -> 'b sclo
2258   | CApp of 'a sval * 'a sval
2259
2260 type 'a sint =
2261   | IVal of 'a sval
2262   | IDo of 'a sval
2263   | ILet of 'a sclo * 'a sfun
2264   | ILift of 'a sclo
2265
2266
2267 type ('a, _) stack =
2268   | EEmp : ('a, top) stack
2269   | ELet : ('a, top) stack * ('a sfun) -> ('a, top) stack
2270   | ELift : ('a, top) stack -> ('a, top) stack
2271   | EHndl : ('a, 'b) stack * 'a sval * 'a sval -> ('a, hnd) stack
2272
2273
2274 type 'a ans =
2275   | AVal of 'a sval
2276   | ADo of 'a sval * ('a, top) stack
2277   | AApp : 'a * 'a sval * ('a, 'b) stack -> 'a ans
2278
2279

```

Fig. 18. Evaluator datatypes for the machine-style presentation.

A.1 Machine-style implementation

We begin by describing an implementation with a first-order¹⁰ representation of semantic functions as closures, following closely the machine presented in Section 7.2. The definitions of semantic constructs are presented in Figure 18, and follow closely the ones of Figure 12. The `sval` and `sfun` types are equipped with natural renaming functions, which allow them to be “shifted” to introduce a fresh variable. While not necessary in the evaluator itself, these are needed for the read-back functions, when going under binders. The data type `sint` represents the intermediate values. Note also that, like the normal forms, the stacks are indexed with `top` or `hnd`.

¹⁰Or near-enough: the environments are represented as functions due to the choice of well-scoped representation of expressions.

```

2296 let rec eval : type a b s. a expr -> (a, b) env -> (b, s) stack -> b ans =
2297   fun e r s -> match e with
2298   | Val v          -> cont s (IVal (mkV v r))
2299   | Let (a, e)     -> cont s (ILet (CPair (a, r), SCl (e, r)))
2300   | Lift e        -> cont s (ILift (CPair (e, r)))
2301   | Do v          -> cont s (IDo (mkV v r))
2302   | App (u, v)    -> apply (mkV u r) (mkV v r) s
2303   | Hndl (e, h, c) -> eval e r (EHndl (s, mkV h r, mkV c r))
2304
2305 and cont : type a s. (a, s) stack -> a sint -> a ans =
2306   fun s i -> match s with
2307   | EHndl (s, h, r)          -> hndl i h r s
2308   | EEmp | ELift _ | ELet _ as s -> top i s
2309
2310 and hndl : type a s. a sint -> a sval -> a sval -> (a, s) stack -> a ans =
2311   fun i h r s -> match i with
2312   | IVal v          -> apply r v s
2313   | ILet (c, f)    -> go c (EHndl (s, h, SFun (SHRet (f, h, r))))
2314   | ILift c        -> cont s (ILet (c, SAppL r))
2315   | IDo v          -> cont s (ILet (CApp (h, v), SAppR r))
2316
2317 and top : type a. a sint -> (a, top) stack -> a ans =
2318   fun i s -> match i with
2319   | IVal v          -> contT s v
2320   | ILet (c, f)    -> go c (ELet (s, f))
2321   | ILift c        -> go c (ELift s)
2322   | IDo v          -> ADo (v, s)
2323
2324 and contT : type a. (a, top) stack -> a sval -> a ans =
2325   fun s v -> match s with
2326   | EEmp          -> AVal v
2327   | ELet (s, f)  -> appFun f v s
2328   | ELift s      -> contT s v
2329
2330 and apply : type a s. a sval -> a sval -> (a, s) stack -> a ans =
2331   fun u v s -> match u with
2332   | SVar x -> AApp (x, v, s)
2333   | SFun f -> appFun f v s
2334
2335 and appFun : type a s. a sfun -> a sval -> (a, s) stack -> a ans =
2336   fun f v s -> match f with
2337   | SCl (e, r)      -> eval e (function None -> v | Some x -> r x) s
2338   | SAppL u        -> apply u v s
2339   | SAppR u        -> apply v u s
2340   | SHRet (f, h, r) -> appFun f v (EHndl (s, h, r))
2341
2342 and go : type a s. a sclo -> (a, s) stack -> a ans =
2343   fun c s -> match c with
2344   | CPair (e, r) -> eval e r s
2345   | CApp (u, v) -> apply u v s

```

Fig. 19. The machine-style evaluator for our calculus.

```

2347 let rec rba : type a. a ans -> a nf =
2348   fun a -> match a with
2349   | AVAl v          -> NV (rbv v)
2350   | ADo (v, s)     -> NC (rbs (NDo (rbv v)) s)
2351   | AApp (x, v, s) -> NC (rbs (NApp (x, rbv v)) s)
2352 and rbv : type a. a sval -> a nv =
2353   fun v -> match v with
2354   | SVar x -> NVar x
2355   | SFun f -> NLam (rbf f)
2356 and rbf : type a. a sfun -> a option nf =
2357   fun f -> rba (appFun (sfshift f) (SVar None) EEmp)
2358 and rbs : type a s. (a, s) nc -> (a, s) stack -> (a, top) nc =
2359   fun n s -> match s with
2360   | EEmp          -> n
2361   | ELet (s, f)   -> rbs (NLet (n, rbf f)) s
2362   | ELift s       -> rbs (NLift n) s
2363   | EHndl (s, h, r) -> rbs (NHndl (n, rbv h, rbv r)) s
2364
2365
2366
2367 let nbe : 'a. 'a expr -> 'a nf =
2368   fun e -> rba (eval e (fun x -> SVar x) EEmp)
2369
2370

```

Fig. 20. The read-back functions and the top-level normalization function for the machine-style evaluator.

The evaluator itself is presented in Figure 19. It differs only cosmetically from the graph presented in Figure 15—mostly by omitting configurations and implementing the interplay of different configurations via mutually recursive functions, in the classic eval-continue style. Note that certain optimisations could be performed: in particular, at a cost of a larger number of transitions, we could compile away the type of semantic closures and inline the go function; however, we believe that the current presentation strikes a good balance between clarity and the number of semantic constructs introduced. Finally, the read-back functions and the top-level normalization function are presented in Figure 20. The only thing of note here is the treatment of variables: since the read-back of a function needs to apply it to a fresh variable (bound by a lambda-abstraction or a let-expression, and represented as `SVar None`), the function needs to be *shifted* to accommodate for a larger set of the free variables.

A.2 Higher-order representation of functions

While the implementation described in the previous section corresponds very closely to the presentation in the main body of the paper and the formalization, we can also *refunctionalise* the datatype of semantic functions (Ager et al. 2003), and use the function space of our chosen meta-language, OCaml, to represent the functions of our calculus. This gives rise to a more uniform treatment of semantic functions, which are now simply appropriately deferred evaluation, but at a cost of a slightly more involved implementation of the remaining parts of the evaluator, since the stacks and answers become mutually inductively defined with values and functions. The definitions are presented in Figure 21. Note that since the semantics is

```

2398 type 'a sval =
2399   | SVar of 'a
2400   | SFun of 'a sfun
2401 and 'a sfun =
2402   {run : 's 'b. ('a -> 'b) -> 'b sval -> ('b, 's) stack -> 'b ans}
2403 and 'a ans =
2404   | AVal of 'a sval
2405   | ADo of 'a sval * ('a, top) stack
2406   | AApp : 'a * 'a sval * ('a, 's) stack -> 'a ans
2407 and ('a, _) stack =
2408   | EEmp : ('a, top) stack
2409   | ELet : ('a, top) stack * 'a sfun -> ('a, top) stack
2410   | ELift : ('a, top) stack -> ('a, top) stack
2411   | EHndl : ('a, 's) stack * 'a sval * 'a sval -> ('a, hnd) stack
2412
2413
2414 type ('a, 'b) env = 'a -> 'b sval
2415
2416
2417 type 'a sclo =
2418   | CPair : 'a expr * ('a, 'b) env -> 'b sclo
2419   | CApp of 'a sval * 'a sval
2420
2421 type 'a sint =
2422   | IVal of 'a sval
2423   | IDo of 'a sval
2424   | ILet of 'a sclo * 'a sfun
2425   | ILift of 'a sclo
2426
2427

```

Fig. 21. Evaluator datatypes for a higher-order representation of functions.

context-sensitive, as locating a stuck-term captures the entire context, the functions need to depend not just on the argument, but also the stack in which they are called. To allow them to be called in different *kinds* of stacks, as well as to bake in the ability to rename the function, we make heavy use of OCaml’s impredicative polymorphism through record fields. On the flipside, this makes “mapping” a function trivial, since the implementation unrolls to a simple function composition.

The evaluator is presented in Figure 22. Note several structural changes with respect to the one discussed in the previous section. Firstly, as expected, the constructors of semantic functions now become auxiliary definitions, some of which were inlined. However, this means that the `mkV` function, which interprets a syntactic value with an environment as a semantic value, is now defined mutually recursively with the evaluator. This is natural, as the interpretation of a lambda-abstraction is the deferred evaluation of its body, and characteristic of any evaluator with this style of representation. Finally, the `appF` function is no longer necessary, as the OCaml function can simply be applied—note that the evaluator never needs to use the renaming capabilities: this is in line with the evaluator from the previous section not using the shifting functions, and with the fact that the evaluators respect scope. In fact,

```

2449 let hret : 'a. 'a sfun -> 'a sval -> 'a sval -> 'a sfun = fun f h r ->
2450   {run = fun g v s -> f.run g v (EHndl (s, svmap g h, svmap g r))}
2451
2452 let rec eval : type a b s. a expr -> (a, b) env -> (b, s) stack -> b ans =
2453   fun e r s -> match e with
2454   | Val v          -> cont (IVal (mkV v r)) s
2455   | App (u, v)     -> apply (mkV u r) (mkV v r) s
2456   | Let (a, e)     -> cont (ILet (CPair (a, r), clos e r)) s
2457   | Lift e        -> cont (ILift (CPair (e, r))) s
2458   | Do v          -> cont (IDo (mkV v r)) s
2459   | Hndl (e, h, c) -> eval e r (EHndl (s, mkV h r, mkV c r))
2460
2461 and cont : type a s. a sint -> (a, s) stack -> a ans =
2462   fun i s -> match s with
2463   | EHndl (s, h, r)          -> hndl i h r s
2464   | EEmp | ELet _ | ELift _ as s -> top i s
2465
2466 and hndl : type a s. a sint -> a sval -> a sval -> (a, s) stack -> a ans =
2467   fun i h r s -> match i with
2468   | IVal v          -> apply r v s
2469   | ILet (c, f) -> go c (EHndl (s, h, SFun (hret f h r)))
2470   | ILift c        -> cont (ILet (c, {run = fun f v -> apply (svmap f r) v})) s
2471   | IDo v          -> cont (ILet (CApp (h, v),
2472     {run = fun f v -> apply v (svmap f r)})) s
2473
2474 and top : type a. a sint -> (a, top) stack -> a ans =
2475   fun i s -> match i with
2476   | IVal v          -> contT v s
2477   | ILet (c, f) -> go c (ELet (s, f))
2478   | ILift c        -> go c (ELift s)
2479   | IDo v          -> ADo (v, s)
2480
2481 and contT : type a. a sval -> (a, top) stack -> a ans =
2482   fun v s -> match s with
2483   | EEmp          -> AVal v
2484   | ELet (s, f) -> f.run (fun x -> x) v s
2485   | ELift s      -> contT v s
2486
2487 and apply : type a s. a sval -> a sval -> (a, s) stack -> a ans =
2488   fun u v s -> match u with
2489   | SVar x -> AApp (x, v, s) | SFun f -> f.run (fun x -> x) v s
2490
2491 and go : type a s. a sclo -> (a, s) stack -> a ans =
2492   fun c s -> match c with
2493   | CPair (e, r) -> eval e r s | CApp (u, v) -> apply u v s
2494
2495 and mkV : type a b. a value -> (a, b) env -> b sval =
2496   fun v r -> match v with
2497   | Lam e -> SFun (clos e r) | Var x -> r x
2498
2499 and clos : type a b. a option expr -> (a, b) env -> b sfun = fun e r ->
   {run = fun f v -> eval e (function None -> v | Some x -> svmap f (r x))}

```

Fig. 22. Evaluator with a higher-order representation of functions.

```

2500 let rec rba : type a. a ans -> a nf =
2501   fun a -> match a with
2502   | AVAl v          -> NV (rbv v)
2503   | ADo (v, s)     -> NC (rbs (NDo (rbv v)) s)
2504   | AApp (x, v, s) -> NC (rbs (NApp (x, rbv v)) s)
2505 and rbv : type a. a sval -> a nv =
2506   fun v -> match v with
2507   | SVar x -> NVar x
2508   | SFun f -> NLam (rbf f)
2509 and rbf : type a. a sfun -> a option nf =
2510   fun f -> rba (f.run (fun x -> Some x) (SVar None) EEmp)
2511 and rbs : type a s. (a, s) nc -> (a, s) stack -> (a, top) nc =
2512   fun n s -> match s with
2513   | EEmp          -> n
2514   | ELet (s, f)   -> rbs (NLet (n, rbf f)) s
2515   | ELift s       -> rbs (NLift n) s
2516   | EHndl (s, h, r) -> rbs (NHndl (n, rbv h, rbv r)) s
2517
2518
2519
2520 let nbe : 'a. 'a expr -> 'a nf =
2521   fun e -> rba (eval e (fun x -> SVar x) EEmp)
2522
2523

```

Fig. 23. The read-back functions and the top-level normalization function for the evaluator with a higher-order representation of functions.

the representation in Figure 21 could be significantly reduced if the evaluator only worked on closed programs—although of course this would render it useless for the purpose of normalization.

The read-back functions (and the top-level normalization function), finally, are presented in Figure 23. Note that these are virtually identical to the ones for a more machine-like representation: this is to be expected, as the shapes of answers, stacks and values remain identical between the two representations. It is only the functions that change, and thus this is where the difference in read-back lies. Since in this representation the function simply requires its arguments, we provide it with a fresh variable and an empty stack—and we only need to make sure that any free variables in the body of the function are accounted for, via the renaming function (`fun x -> Some x`) that ensures that the variable passed as the argument is, in fact, fresh.

The presence of the stacks in the evaluator may be disconcerting to some readers. We note that this is due to the context-sensitive nature of the cases where stuck answers are produced. We could refunctionalise the data type of stacks to obtain an evaluator in some form of CPS (Ager et al. 2003). Mapping this continuation-passing evaluator to direct style, however, seems to require control operators (Danvy and Filinski 1990) to capture the continuations required by the shape of stuck answers.